

TC FOR BE

TRANSFORMATIVE CHANGE FOR BIODIVERSITY & EQUITY

Grant agreement number: 101082057

DELIVERABLE 3.1

Finance instruments and related regulations

Lead party for deliverable: Hanken – Hanken Svenska Handelshögskolan

Document type: R

Due date of deliverable: 01-12-2024

Actual submission date: 30-11-2024

Version: 1.2

Dissemination level: Public

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WP	Task	Deliverable	Authors (lead and others)	Participant organisation	Dissemination level	Report Date & Version	Deliverable Delivery date (month)
3	3.1	D3.1	Theresia Harrer, Othmar Lehner, Eva-Maria Öhlinger, Truc Thanh Van	Hanken	PUB	V1.2 10.1.2025	24

Partners

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Citation: Theresia Harrer, Othmar Lehner, Eva-Maria Öhlinger, Truc Thanh Van (2024) Finance instruments and related regulations as levers for change for biodiversity protection from the EU. D3.1 TCforBE Hanken - Hanken Svenska Handelshögskolan

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Summary

Biodiversity loss ranks among the foremost global risks, threatening the very foundation of life on Earth. This report, Deliverable 3.1 of Work Package 3 of the EU's Horizon Research Program's funded TCforBE project, addresses the identification, assessment and development of global transformative investment and finance levers for biodiversity and equity, and the urgent need for robust financial instruments to help stem this loss and foster recovery in an equitable way.

The report opens by highlighting the gravity of the issue, noting a devastating reduction in global wildlife populations and a significant degradation of natural habitats. It sets the stage by outlining pivotal global and EU initiatives, such as the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework and the European Green Deal. These initiatives underscore the financial sector's potential to drive change through strategic investments in biodiversity conservation.

Diverse financial instruments are available to support biodiversity. A dedicated section assesses their effectiveness in leveraging economic incentives for nature conservation (comprises both nature restoration and protection) and social equity. Despite growing funds, current financial contributions fall short of the annual US\$824 billion needed for nature restoration. This gap highlights the pressing need for innovative solutions to effectively deploy existing financial instruments.

Further this report reviews strategic actions by the EU and its Member States aimed at addressing biodiversity loss. These actions are evaluated for their alignment with the EU's biodiversity strategy goals, focusing on minimizing drivers of biodiversity loss, enhancing governance, and protecting and restoring nature. This section provides a critical examination of the effectiveness of these strategies in achieving the EU's biodiversity objectives.

The final section delves into the strengths and weaknesses of policy levers within the EU impacting biodiversity finance. It identifies significant gaps, such as the need for clearer regulatory frameworks and the alignment of financial incentives. The report suggests that more robust regulatory mandates and a deeper integration of biodiversity goals could significantly enhance the impact of EU biodiversity policies.

The report concludes by synthesizing findings and underscoring the substantial gaps in biodiversity financing and policy implementation. It calls for an intensified commitment from both public and private sectors to bridge the funding gap. Recommendations are offered to policymakers and industry stakeholders to improve the efficacy of biodiversity finance instruments and ensure sustainable and equitable conservation efforts.

At a glance: This report captures the essence of the challenges and opportunities within the biodiversity finance sector. It serves as a guide for stakeholders, outlining a range of financial instruments and strategic actions that can contribute to more effective biodiversity conservation. The report highlights the urgent need for action using finance as an entry point in all sectors—government, private, and civil society—and recommends focusing efforts on scaling up biodiversity finance to meet this global challenge.

Introduction – The need for biodiversity policy and finance

In the midst of escalating biodiversity loss, which now ranks among the most critical global crises (IPCC, 2023), this report examines the essential role of finance instruments and regulations in supporting the agrifood sector's transition toward sustainable and equitable biodiversity practices. This exploration is conducted under the auspices of the EU Horizon Research Program funded TCforBE project's Work Package 3 on Financing for Biodiversity, which seeks to deepen understanding and refine the tools available that support positive biodiversity outcomes.

Biodiversity is fundamental to the resilience of ecosystems and by extension, human survival and economic stability (CBD, 2021). Recent studies underscore the severity of the biodiversity crisis, noting a precipitous decline in global wildlife populations, with the World Wildlife Fund's Living Planet Report highlighting an average 68% decrease in population sizes of mammals, birds, amphibians, reptiles, and fish between 1970 and 2016 (Almond et al., 2022). The degradation and loss of habitats further compound the crisis. In their landmark report (2019), the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES) argues that five factors drive biodiversity loss most (see figure 1): 1) pollution, 2) direct exploitation of organisms, 3) land and sea-use change, 4) climate change, and 5) invasive alien species. In outlining these drivers, the IPBES (2019) also calls for urgent and effective interventions. Against this backdrop, biodiversity policies and finance emerges as crucial areas for action (Buschke et al., 2019; Deutz et al., 2020; OECD, 2019; Rampling et al., 2024; Seidl et al., 2020; Smith et al., 2020).

Figure 1: Biodiversity loss driver impact per realm (IPBES, 2019)

The potential and current role of financial instruments and regulations in addressing biodiversity loss is multi-dimensional and complex. For example, the integration of biodiversity concerns into financial decision-making involves developing mechanisms that can efficiently channel funds into biodiversity-positive activities while discouraging investments that harm the environment (Nedopil, 2022). International efforts, such as those under the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), have long recognized the need for robust financial mechanisms to support the global biodiversity agenda. The CBD's Aichi Biodiversity Targets explicitly called for enhanced financial resources to improve the state of biodiversity. However, as the 2020 deadline passed, it has become evident that most of the targets were not met, signifying a substantial gap between policy objectives and their implementation (UN, 2022).

On a European level, the European Union has been proactive in embedding biodiversity considerations into its policy framework. For example, the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 is part of the European Green Deal, aiming to lead the way towards an ecologically sustainable future. This strategy outlines ambitious plans, including establishing legally binding nature restoration targets and measures to enable transformative change through a systemic approach across multiple sectors and scales. This report will delve into these strategic actions, examining their alignment with broader EU objectives and their effectiveness in addressing the root causes of biodiversity loss.

The financial sector – defined as a distinct organizational field, characterized by a set of institutions, actors, and practices that are structured around the creation, management, and distribution of

financial resources (Dörry, 2015) – plays a dual role as potential facilitators of and barriers to equitable biodiversity conservation (Flammer et al., 2023; Löfqvist et al., 2023). With significant control over global financial flows, this sector is uniquely positioned to influence environmental outcomes through their investment choices. This report evaluates existing financial instruments dedicated to biodiversity, such as green bonds and biodiversity offsets, alongside newer models like biodiversity-positive impact investments and conservation finance. Despite growing interest and investment in these areas (see e.g., Flammer et al., 2023), the current scale of financial flows is still insufficient compared to the estimated funds required to tackle global biodiversity challenges.

The following sections of the report provide a detailed examination of these dynamics:

- A discussion of the conceptual evolution of biodiversity as it pertains to ecological, economic, and regulatory frameworks related to finance.
- An overview of global and EU-specific biodiversity initiatives, illustrating the transition from fragmented efforts to more cohesive and integrated biodiversity policy frameworks.
- An analysis of key levers of change in the EU's biodiversity policy, highlighting critical mechanisms that may influence the effective execution of political goals and finance instruments.
- An overview of the biodiversity finance landscape, identifying existing financial instruments as well as their benefits and weaknesses.
- A critical evaluation of the EU biodiversity policy and biodiversity finance landscape, considering their alignment with the global conservation agenda and the scientific evidence provided by the landmark report of the IPBES (2019).

Summing up, this report provides an overview of EU biodiversity policies and biodiversity finance options. It furthermore synthesizes this overview, identifying critical gaps and opportunities within biodiversity financing and policy implementation within the EU. It advocates for strengthened commitment across both public and private sectors to bridge these gaps, with targeted recommendations aimed at enhancing the effectiveness of financial instruments and ensuring the sustainability of conservation efforts. By furnishing a comprehensive analysis of the potential and limitations of EU legislation and financial instruments in fostering biodiversity, this document aims to serve as a foundational resource for stakeholders engaged in shaping the future of biodiversity conservation. Through this academic and practical inquiry, the report contributes to the ongoing discourse on how best to finance biodiversity in a manner that is both effective and sustainable, providing valuable insights for policymakers, industry leaders, and conservation advocates alike.

Methodology

To identify all relevant biodiversity regulations and finance instruments we employed mixed methods (Creswell et al., 2003; Edmondson & McManus, 2007). **First**, we sketched and assessed the biodiversity policy landscape by identifying key biodiversity initiatives and policy documents. To do so, we employed a qualitative network analysis (Lury et al., 2018) followed by a qualitative document analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2012). Qualitative Network Analysis (QNA) refers to a methodological approach within social network analysis that focuses on understanding the nature of connections between entities (like individuals, groups, or organizations) from a qualitative perspective. This approach is distinct from a traditional quantitative network analysis, which typically relies on numerical data and statistical methods to understand network structures and dynamics. QNA aims to uncover the relevant actors in a network and the underlying relationships between those actors. As such it provided an excellent tool to identify key biodiversity investment and finance initiatives and related policy documents. The document analysis following Braun and Clarke (2012) is an established approach to identify thematic foci in data. As such it helped us to analyze the content of the identified biodiversity investment and finance policy documents and extract their relevant thematic foci.

We started by purposefully identifying key biodiversity initiatives and policy documents (based on visibility and prominence in media). Our initial focus was on global initiatives (including among others the CBD, the IUCN, and the GRI). From there, we followed the principles of QNA and iteratively identified all relevant biodiversity initiatives and policy documents (e.g., the IPBES Global Assessment Report 2019, and the GBF). The EU here quickly emerged as central player in the biodiversity policy landscape. Accordingly, we collected EU policy documents such as the EU Taxonomy, the CSRD, and the EU's Biodiversity Strategy. When the search did not reveal new biodiversity initiatives and policy documents, we focused on the analysis of these documents. Building on the principles of Braun and Clarke (2012), we began by identifying the thematic foci in the documents. These foci were the overall policy approach (e.g., coercion or normativity), policy focus (e.g., biodiversity loss driver reduction, nature restoration or protection). We then also identified the key levers of change for biodiversity.

Second, we assessed the biodiversity finance landscape. For this, we utilized three different panel datasets: Bloomberg, MSCI, and the assessment data from the Principles of Responsible Investing (PRI). Bloomberg and MSCI are regarded as the most important ESG reporting databases (Berg et al., 2022). Accordingly, we used these to assess the state of biodiversity finance on a global level. Biodiversity finance instruments were identified either by their descriptor (e.g., biodiversity bond) or by the project description (e.g. a green bond aiming to achieve biodiversity outcomes). PRI is the largest network of sustainable investors globally. Investors who subscribe to PRI principles commit to reporting their sustainable investing activities annually. The PRI assessment data used for this report covers global investor self-reported data on their sustainable investing activities across major asset classes from 2016-2020. We used this data to identify how investors considered biodiversity. Where possible we conducted simple quantitative analyses (Bloomberg and MSCI). If not possible (notably PRI), we performed a keyword search and through this iteratively identified relevant investors, assets classes, and strategic foci. The keywords were “*biodiversity*”, “*natur*”, and “*nature-positive*”.

Glossary

See [TCforBE glossary](#) for key terms and definitions.

Defining Biodiversity

Before we present the results of our analysis, we want to clarify what biodiversity means. In the following paragraphs we trace and review the most important biodiversity definitions. These are also presented in the [TCforBE project glossary](#) which is a work in progress.

Ecologists have discussed plants, animals, species, and the diversity of these, for centuries. They usually refer to the biosphere and provide insights into the diversity of species and faunas. For example, in their theory of island biogeography, MacArthur and Wilson (1967) note that a ten-fold increase in land equals a doubling of species diversity. Similarly, studying the small island off South America, New Guinea, and Indonesia, Terborgh (1974) note that the smaller the area (e.g., island), the faster species and faunas go extinct. Willis (1979) and van Valen (1973) make similar observations. The biosphere, thus, was mostly about the flora and fauna, and how their diversity developed as land changed.

Although land use change caused by human intervention has recently been identified as the main driver of biodiversity loss (IPBES, 2019), until the late 20th century the biosphere was primarily discussed without considering the role of people in land change. The first to explicitly link humanity to the biosphere was The International Union for Conservation of Nature and Natural Resources (IUCN, 1980). In the *World Conservation Strategy*, they suggested that the biosphere was critical for humanity, yet the conservation of living resources was seldom discussed in the realm of sustainable development. As a result, most developing countries saw the conservation of living resources as irrelevant or even harmful to development efforts and social justice. Against this background, the IUCN proposed the first global strategy for the conservation of living resources with the aim to restore balance among conservation and development.

Once the biosphere had been linked to human development, the conservation of ecosystems and living resources became increasingly important. This required explicit attention to the diversity of the species and faunas, which then also resulted in a change of terminology from the practice- (and biology-) driven term “biosphere” to a more general and philosophical term “biological diversity” (Christian, 2014). The new term appeared first in 1980, when Michael Soulé and Bruce Wilcox edited a book on conservation biology. In the book’s foreword Thomas Lovejoy introduced the term biological diversity, referring to it as the number of species present in a group.

The first to explicitly mention the term biodiversity was the renowned Harvard biologist Edward O. Wilson. He edited the proceedings of the first National Forum on BioDiversity that took place in Washington D.C. in 1986, and in those proceedings noted that the term biodiversity blends “biological diversity” or “biotic diversity” (Wilson, 1988). Both terms refer to the diversity of organisms. However, the prior term is broader and includes abiotic factors such as minerals, water, and air.

The 1992 Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) of the UN offered the first global definition of biodiversity as

“the variability among living organisms from all sources including, inter alia, terrestrial, marine, and other aquatic ecosystems and the ecological complexes of which they are part; this includes diversity within species, between species, and of ecosystems.” (UN, 1992, p. 2)

Based on this definition, biodiversity refers to the variety of organisms in ecosystems, and this variety can be assessed through three types of diversity: 1) Genetic diversity (within species), 2) species diversity (between species), and 3) ecosystems diversity (see Farnham, 2007 for a comprehensive overview of how the types emerged).

For the next two decades, the 1992 has not been developed significantly. Only in 2019, when the issue of the unprecedented biodiversity loss moved up on the global policy agenda, the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES) published its Global Assessment Report on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. In this report it extended the original 1992 definition of biodiversity to

“The variability among living organisms from all sources including terrestrial, marine, and other aquatic ecosystems and the ecological complexes of which they

are a part. This includes variation in genetic, phenotypic, phylogenetic, and functional attributes, as well as changes in abundance and distribution over time and space within and among species, biological communities, and ecosystems.” (p. 1033)

This new definition not only extends biodiversity beyond the three original types of diversity (genetic, species, and ecosystem diversity). Crucially it also, for the first time, includes notions of inter-species and -ecosystem justice (keyword “over time”) (Deutz et al., 2020). The 2019 definition of the IPBES was also adopted by The Global Biodiversity Framework (GBF) or Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (UN, 2022). This report also adopts the IPBES’ definition.

Global biodiversity initiatives as background

TcforBE investigated international biodiversity governance initiatives in Work Package 2, [Deliverable 2.1 on International biodiversity governance initiatives](#), providing an overview of international governance and policy agreements and initiatives, and EU level policies, laws and regulations related to agrifood systems and biodiversity. Many of these initiatives have developed policies related to finance instruments and measurement frameworks. The following section traces the development of the most important initiatives (for a detailed overview see Appendix 1) and groups them by purpose.

The International Union for Conservation of Nature and Natural Resources (IUCN) was one of the first initiatives that emerged specifically with the purpose of protecting nature. As shown in figure 2, it emerged as early as in 1948. 40 years later, Ceres – a non-profit organization that emerged in response to the Exxon Valdez oil spill – was formed to work with investors to protect and restore life on land. A few years later, in 1992, the United Nations held the first Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD). The World Business Council for Sustainable Development (WBCSD), the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) and the Carbon Disclosure Project (CDP) also emerged before the turn of the century. The Capitals Coalition (CC) developed in the early 2000s.

Although numerous initiatives have emerged around the globe, the debates on biodiversity and the challenges related to its loss really started around 2010. At that time the CBD developed the first global Biodiversity Targets (then called Aichi Targets) during their summit in Nagoya. As part of these targets the CDB also set up the first global Strategic Plan for Biodiversity, with the intention of it to be implemented from 2011-2020.

Figure 2: Global biodiversity policy initiatives

After the development of the Aichi Targets and the first global Strategic Plan for Biodiversity, numerous initiatives with an either implicit or explicit goal to protect nature emerged. Among the most important ones are the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which were developed in Rio de Janeiro in 2012 (see again figure 1). The Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES) developed was also established in 2012.

Another noteworthy event is the incorporation of the Science-Based Targets for Nature (SBTN) in 2015. It aims to develop methods that help companies and cities to set clear and integrated targets across earth systems. From 2015 onwards more initiatives emerged. Among them is the World Benchmarking Alliance (WBA), the Partnership for Biodiversity Accounting Financials (PBAF), the Business for Nature (BfN) coalition, and most notably the Taskforce for Nature Related Financial Disclosures (TNFD). During this time, the CBD also worked to renew its 2010 Strategic Plan for Biodiversity, which included the Aichi targets. In 2022 the plan and the targets were replaced by the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (GBF). The GBF lays out 4 global goals until 2050 and 23 global goals until 2030. Among those 2030 goals is, for example, the goal to protect and conserve 30% of land and 30% of oceans by 2030 (30x30 goal).

Looking at the biodiversity initiatives' purposes, our analysis indicates that they can be grouped into four broad categories: 1) awareness & intergovernmental alignment, 2) data providers, 3) financing, 4) measurement and reporting standard setters. Table 1 outlines each initiative's purpose. Overall, it shows that most initiatives aim to develop and harmonize biodiversity accounting and measurement frameworks (see "measurement and reporting standard setter"). The second largest group aims to raise global awareness and harmonize views and interpretations of biodiversity (see awareness & intergovernmental alignment). Others aim to integrate biodiversity into decision-

making in the financial sector (see “financing” in table 1) and develop data availability for better biodiversity reporting (see “data providers” in table 1). Related to these different purposes, the initiatives also have different target audiences.

Purpose	Initiative	Abbrev.	Target audience
Awareness & intergovernmental alignment	Business for Nature	BfN	Corporates
	Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services	IPBES	Public, private and non-governmental organizations
	International Union for Conservation of Nature	IUCN	Public, private and non-governmental organizations
	Sustainable Development Goals	SDGs	Public, private and non-governmental organizations
	The Convention on Biological Diversity	CBD	Public, private and non-governmental organizations
Data providers	Accountability Accelerator	GCAA	Corporates
	Carbon Disclosure Project	CDP	Corporates
	World Benchmarking Alliance	WBA	Public, private and non-governmental organizations
Financing	Ceres		Financial institutions
	Finance for biodiversity pledge	FfB	Financial institutions
	Planet Tracker		Financial institutions
	Share Action		Financial institutions
Measurement and reporting standard setter	Capitals Coalition	CC	Corporates
	Global Reporting Initiative	GRI	Corporates
	International Integrated Reporting Council	IIRC	Corporates
	Natural Capital finance alliance	NCFA	Financial institutions
	Partnership for Biodiversity Accounting Financials	PBAF	Financial institutions
	Science-based targets for nature	SBTN	Corporates
	Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures	TNFD	Corporates
	World business council for sustainable development	WBCSD	Corporates

Table 1: Global biodiversity policy initiatives clustered by purpose

EU Biodiversity policy initiatives

Mirroring the above global developments, the EU has ramped up its efforts to halt biodiversity loss as well. Overall, the issues of biodiversity and biodiversity loss have been important in the EU for quite a while. For example, the first biodiversity-related directive was published as early as in 1992 (when the original 1992 Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) of the UN was held). Yet, as shown in figure 3, from 2018 onwards the EU published significantly more biodiversity policy documents. Before we discuss these documents in more detail, our analysis revealed that the EU has issued 31 dedicated biodiversity policy documents over 30 years (see figure 3 below for a timeline and for a detailed overview see appendix 2a).

Figure 3: Development of EU strategic frameworks and legislations with relevance for biodiversity

Building on the overview of the EU's biodiversity policy documents, the next sections discuss three aspects of them: 1) the EU's policy approach to biodiversity (i.e. coercive or normative), 2) the thematic foci of the EU's biodiversity policy (e.g., nature protection or biodiversity loss driver minimization), and 3) the key levers of change foreseen in the EU's biodiversity policy (i.e., biodiversity indicators and strategic actions).

EU policy approach: From coercion to normativity

The EU's biodiversity policy documents can be divided into **strategic frameworks** and **legislations**. **Strategic frameworks** refer to communications and proposal documents and outline a normative vision related to biodiversity (e.g., the EU Biodiversity Strategy aims to protect nature and reverse the degradation of ecosystems by 2030). In comparison, **legislation** refers to regulations and directives which specify policy pathways and goals to be implemented by each EU member state (they are therefore coercive). Depending on the group to which the EU's policy documents can be ascribed to, the underlying policy approach can be identified.

Figure 4 shows the chronological issuance of strategic frameworks and regulations. A closer look at the figure, reveals that from 1992 until the mid-2000s the EU focused primarily on developing regulations and directives. These concerned primarily the sustainable use of commodities (e.g., timber), species (e.g., birds), and other natural resources (e.g., water). Given that regulations and directives are **legislations**, the EU's initial biodiversity policy focus was characterized by direct (coercive) enforcement. Figure 6 demonstrates this.

Figure 4: Policy publications from 1992-2018

This coercive approach changed from 2019 onwards. While to this date the EU issued primarily legislations (i.e., directives and regulations) (see figures 5 and 6), the publication of the European Green Deal marked the issuance of the first major normative **strategic framework** (i.e., communication). The European Green Deal contains various "policy initiatives [...] with the ultimate goal of reaching climate neutrality by 2050" (European Commission, 2020). As part of its publication the EU issued numerous proposals of the documents. It also issued other accompanying strategic frameworks, including the circular economy plan, the biodiversity strategy, and the farm to fork strategy. Taken together these strategic frameworks marked an important shift in the EU's policy approach to biodiversity. While until 2018 the EU focused on legislations (i.e., regulations and directives, see figure 4 above), from 2019 onwards over 35% of the EU's publications were communications and another 6% were related proposals that were issued for discussion. The EU's biodiversity policies thus increasingly focused on **strategic frameworks** (instead of legislations), and as such shifted from a rather coercive approach to a normative one. Figure 7 highlights this increased normativity in the EU's biodiversity policy.

Figure 5: Policy publications from 2019-2023

The figures already show that the EU has significantly changed its biodiversity policy approach (from coercion to normativity). Tables 2 and 3 further substantiate this shift, by showing that until 2019 (table 2) the EU’s biodiversity policies required high levels of subject knowledge (e.g., related to species). As such the sponsoring Directorate Generals of the regulations and directives were primarily subject experts (i.e., the DG environment).

Directorate-General	Name of policy	Publication type
DG Environment	Birds Directive	Directive
	Habitats Directive	Directive
	Timber Regulation	Regulation
	Water Framework Directive	Directive
	Invasive Alien Species	Regulation
	Marine Strategy Framework Directive	Directive
	DG Health and Food Safety	Food information to consumers
Sustainable use of pesticides Directive		Directive
DG Agriculture and Rural Development	Organic production and labelling	Regulation
DG Climate Action	Land use, land use change and forestry Regulation	Regulation
DG Energy	Use of Energy from renewable sources	Directive
DG Maritime Affairs and Fisheries	EU Common Fisheries Policy	Regulation

Table 2: Directorate Generals sponsoring the EU's biodiversity policies (1992-2018)

After 2019 (table 3), the EU’s biodiversity policies continued to be based on subject expertise. These subject experts were now increasingly tasked with the drafting of normative communication documents (e.g., the Biodiversity Strategy). The regulations and directives, in comparison, increasingly required financial market expertise. Key regulations and directives such as the SFDR, the Taxonomy Regulation, and the CSRD, are, for example, sponsored by the Directorate Generals Financial Stability, Financial Services and Capital Markets Union. Thus, while biodiversity subject experts are involved in drafting normative biodiversity goals, the operationalization of these goals is delegated to financial market experts, who face the task of linking biodiversity with finance rationales.

Directorate-General	Name of policy	Publication type
DG Environment	EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030	Communication
	EU Pollinators Initiative	Communication
	EU Soil Strategy for 2030	Communication
	New Circular Economy Action Plan	Communication
	New EU Forest Strategy for 2030	Communication
	Revision of the EU action plan against wildlife trafficking	Communication
	Nature restoration Regulation	Proposal
	Action Plan: Towards Zero Pollution for Air, Water and Soil	Communication
DG Financial Stability, Financial Services and Capital Markets Union	Sustainability-related disclosures in the financial services sector	Regulation
	Sustainable Europe Investment Plan	Communication
	Taxonomy Regulation	Regulation
	Corporate sustainability reporting Directive	Directive
	European green bond Regulation	Proposal
DG Agriculture and Rural Development	Action Plan for the development of organic production	Communication
	Common Market Organization regulation	Regulation
	Regulation on financing the CAP	Regulation
	CAP strategic plan Regulation	Regulation
DG Health and Food Safety	Farm to Fork Strategy	Communication
DG for Communication	European Green Deal	Communication

Table 3: Directorate Generals sponsoring the EU's biodiversity policies (2019-2024)

Policy focus: Biodiversity loss driver minimization

While the policy approach is important to understand how the EU aims to promote biodiversity in its member states, it is also critical to understand what the EU aims to promote with its biodiversity policy. We, thus, also analyzed the thematic foci of the EU's biodiversity policy.

Our analysis reveals six focus areas of the EU's biodiversity policy: 1) biodiversity loss driver minimization, 2) provision of more adequate biodiversity financing, 3) development of biodiversity governance structures, 4) nature protection, 5) nature restoration, and 6) support activities (e.g., education). Figure 6 below shows that most of the EU's policy efforts are directed towards biodiversity loss driver minimization (35%), closely followed by nature protection (23%) and the development of biodiversity financing opportunities (19%). The development of governance structures (10%) represents only a minor policy focus, and nature restoration and support activities (both 6%) receive the least policy attention.

Figure 6: Focus areas of EU biodiversity policies

Given the primary focus of EU biodiversity policy on biodiversity loss driver minimization (35% in figure 6), we conducted a further analysis of the types of drivers these policies seek to address. Overall, our analysis revealed that EU biodiversity policies address all five major biodiversity loss drivers identified by the IPBES (2019). However, the drivers are not addressed equally. Figure 7 highlights that with 37% and 36% respectively, the drivers of pollution and direct exploitation of organisms are the biggest focus of EU policies. With an approximate addressing rate of 9%, the drivers land- and sea-use change, climate change, and invasive alien species all represent a minor policy focus.

Figure 7: Biodiversity driver policy focus

Critical levers of change

The previous sections review the EU's biodiversity policy approach to addressing different biodiversity loss drivers. They do, however, not discuss the key mechanisms (i.e., levers) within the policies through which the EU aims to promote change for biodiversity. These mechanisms go beyond the policy approach (normative vs. coercive) as they outline concrete means through which the proposed policy aims to influence social structures and processes and create pathways for change. Understanding such mechanisms is, thus, critical to comprehend potential (adverse) effects of the EU's biodiversity efforts. In the next sections we review the two key mechanisms or levers of change which emerged from our analysis: 1) biodiversity indicators and metrics, and 2) strategic actions.

Lever of Change 1: Biodiversity Indicators and Metrics

A critical part of the EU's biodiversity policy is the introduction of biodiversity indicators and metrics. Three legislative texts are at the core of this: 1) Regulation (EU) 2019/2088 aka "Sustainable Finance Disclosure Regulation (SFDR)", Regulation (EU) 2020/852 aka "Taxonomy Regulation (TR)", and notably the European Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS) put forward in the Appendix of Directive (EU) 2022/2464, referred to as the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD). Those three texts contribute to the EU's biodiversity goals not only by putting forward a comprehensive corporate disclosure framework, but also by introducing a raster of biodiversity indicators and metrics. Given that corporate accountability is a critical aspect in achieving the EU's biodiversity goals, and disclosure systems indicators are key to instigate such accountability (Roberts & Scapens, 1985), the indicators and metrics put forward by the three legislative texts can be regarded as key levers of change.

The effectiveness of the indicators and metrics depends on how well they contribute to the EU's policy foci and goals (i.e., biodiversity loss driver minimization, protection and restoration of nature, financing, governance). The following paragraphs thus present our results about how the indicators and metrics contribute to the EU's policy foci.

These results are based on a comprehensive review of relevant biodiversity indicators and metrics (see appendix 2b for details), and on an assessment of the underlying accounting logic of the larger corporate disclosure framework outlined in the three central legislative texts (SFDR, TR, CSRD/ESRS). To provide the necessary background, the next section briefly introduces the main biodiversity accounting approaches and their underlying logics. We then present our results on how the EU's corporate disclosure framework adopts these accounting logics, and regarding the indicators and metrics put forward in this framework.

Biodiversity accounting approaches and logics

In literature three main approaches to biodiversity accounting can be determined: inventory, ecosystem, and cost approach.

The inventory approach aims to recognize the (economic) value of natural capital, whereas the ecosystem approach aims to recognize contributions of ecosystem services. The cost approach aims to recognize the costs of restoration activities. The **(natural) inventory approach** was proposed and tested by Jones (1996, 2003). It is based on the logic of the resource-based view of the firm (Barney, 1991) and sees biodiversity as necessary resource to organizations. To assess biodiversity, the natural inventory approach thus focuses on tracking stocks of habitat based on a pyramid of hierarchical criticality (see figure 8). This pyramid presents inventory categories of habitats as well as critical and non-critical flora and fauna. As such it is divided into six levels. Levels five and six are the most general, focusing on creating a general inventory of flora and fauna by species and population. Level three and four focus on critical habitats only and on creating an inventory of their respective flora and fauna by species and population. Level two focuses on creating an inventory of flora and fauna that are listed or protected. The first level, as the tip of the pyramid, then focuses on a categorization of the type of habitat (e.g., woodland) by its natural capital status (critical or non-critical).

Figure 8: Pyramid of hierarchical criticality (Jones, 1996, p. 291)

Jones (1996) also puts forward a simple ecological evaluation of the levels. He suggests that critical habitat is priceless and cannot be ascribed any value. In contrast, non-critical habitat can be ascribed an economic value. To capture this economic value, Jones (1996) suggests a simple ranking of the habitats on a 1-5 scale (1 being a habitat with high worth, 5 being one with little worth), and a collation of this ranking into a (natural) inventory. By relating organizational activities to changes in this inventory, the inventory approach offers a useful way to recognize organizations affect natural capital. Overall, the inventory approach recognizes stocks of natural capital as valuable and partly even invaluable good (Jones, 2014). However, it also largely separates humans from nature and suggests the latter is readily available for use.

The **ecosystems approach** was most notably developed by Houdet et al. (2009), Costanza et al. (1997), and Daily (1997). In comparison to the inventory approach, it assesses biodiversity through life cycle thinking and by identifying the pressures on so-called ecosystem services. Ecosystem services are the basis of all functioning ecosystems and as such they are critical for biodiversity. According to the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (2005) we can distinguish between four ecosystem services:

- provisioning (e.g., timber, water, fiber, food, etc.)
- regulatory (e.g., pollination, flood control, etc.)
- supporting (e.g., photosynthesis, nutrient cycling, etc.)
- cultural (e.g., spiritual, recreational, aesthetic, etc.)

The ecosystems approach of biodiversity accounting proposes to assess the impact on biodiversity by tracking physical flows (i.e., inputs and outputs) and by relating these flows to the four ecosystem

services. Houdet et al. (2009) build on the UNDS (2001) and propose that flows can be tracked by looking at the following inputs and outputs.

Input (in kg/kWh)	Output in kg
Raw materials	Product
Auxiliary materials	Main product
Packaging	By products
Operating materials	Waste
Merchandise	Municipal waste
Energy	Recycled waste
Gas	Hazardous waste
Coal	Wastewater
Fuel oil	Amount
Other fuels	Heavy materials
District heat	COD
Renewables (biomass, wood)	BOD
Solar, wind, water produced electricity	Air-emissions CO ₂
Water	NO _x
Municipal water	SO ₂
Ground water	Dust
Spring water	FCKWs, NH ₄ ; VOCs
Rain, surface water	Ozone depleting substances

Table 4: Common physical flows (depicted in inputs and outputs) (Houdet et al., 2009)

To relate physical flows to ecosystem services, Houdet et al. (2009) propose that organizations identify potentially relevant actors in and around their value chain. Where do they get which resources from? Who consumes the end products and in which quantity? Starting with those questions, an organization can sketch the relevant areas it operates in, and from there assess the flows within and between those areas. Most importantly, by relating the flows to different market prices, the economic value of the ecosystem service contributions can be determined (Houdet et al., 2009). Overall, the ecosystem approach offers an opportunity to recognize nature, humans and organizations as part of one ecosystem (Accorsi et al., 2016; Costanza et al., 2014; Feger & Mermet, 2017; Houdet et al., 2012; Liu et al., 2013). Yet, as Jones and Solomon (2013) cautions, this recognition depends on nature providing ecosystem services that are of use to people.

Lastly, the **cost approach** to biodiversity accounting is advocated for by Rubenstein (1992), Bebbington and Gray (2001), Davies (2013), and Antheaume (2004). The premise behind it is that organizational actions usually create and destroy value along a value chain (notably recognized in the profit and loss statement). While this is widely accepted, prices and expenditures in conventional accounting do not recognize the full societal and environmental costs from economic decisions and actions (e.g., related to avoidance, restoration, or damage costs) (Baxter & Chua, 2003; Gray & Laughlin, 2012). Rather, they treat them as unquantifiable externalities (Bebbington & Gray, 2001; Boiral, 2016). The cost approach to biodiversity accounting thus aims to remedy this overlooking of externalities via a correction of market prices in the balance sheet (Antheaume, 2004; Davies, 2014).

Rubenstein (1992) was advocated for a “green balance sheet” which recognizes nature restoration costs through the profit and loss statement. Quattrone et al. (2023) operationalized these ideas of a green a balance sheet in the so-called Sustainable Value Table (SVT) (see example in table 5).

	€ in Y1	SDG 1	SDG 2	SDG 6	SDG 10
Economic Revenues					
Cost of production and services			-(X)	-(X)	
Value added by operating activities					
Interest received					
Dividends received					
Economic wealth created					
Employees (through wages, etc.)					

	€ in Y1	SDG 1	SDG 2	SDG 6	SDG 10
Providers of interest-bearing capital (through interest)					
<i>Nature (through provision)</i>			+(X)	+(X)	
The state (through tax)					
The firm (through retained earnings)					
Shareholders (through dividends)					
Economic wealth distributed					

Table 5: Example of cost BA approach (Quattrone et al., 2023, pp. 7-9)

The starting point of the SVT is the regular profit and loss statement. Each expense item is assessed regarding whether it contributes to an SDG. Once established, organizations can assess whether the expense item contributes to the respective SDG, negatively or positively. If contributions are negative (i.e., cause damage or require restoration), they then need to be compensated for. This compensation can be recognized in monetary terms as a provision (see the cursive item “Nature” in table 5). Overall, the cost approach to biodiversity accounting adopts a system perspective (recognizing humans and nature as critical parts of a system) and, through the focus on damage, recognizes the needs of future generations/nature.

Overall, while all biodiversity accounting approaches aim to assess biodiversity, they do so differently (see table 6 below for an overview). The **inventory and ecosystem approach**, for instance, focuses on physical approaches. The natural inventory approach intends to track physical stocks of natural capital. Similarly, the ecosystem approach aims to understand physical flows as well as dependencies and impacts on ecosystem services. The **cost approach**, in contrast, is a monetary approach. Instead of assessing stocks or impacts/dependencies, its intention is to estimate potential damage through economic value creation and based on it the costs of the efforts needed to restore/protect nature.

	(Natural) inventory approach	Ecosystem approach	Cost approach
Motivation to recognize	Natural assets	Contributions to ecosystem services	Avoidance or restoration costs
Focus on	Stocks	Flows	Potential damage
Classifies nature as	Commodity	Asset	Asset
Underlying value(s)	Instrumental but can have intrinsic connotations	Instrumental	Instrumental & relational
Underlying logic	Primarily anthropocentric	Anthropocentric	Non-Anthropocentric
Examples	STAR metric, IUCN Red list	CICES , TESSA , or ARIES	Green balance sheet, Sustainable Values
Key works	(Jones, 1996, 2003)	(Constanza, 1997; Houdet et al., 2009)	(Antheaume, 2004; Rubenstein, 1992)
Main criticism	Commodification of nature	Anthropocentric	Financialization of nature

Table 6: Three main biodiversity accounting approaches

The approaches also classify nature differently. The inventory approach, for instance, emphasizes that nature’s value changes as it is being used (i.e., the stocks increase or reduce). It therefore classifies nature as a commodity. In comparison, the ecosystem and cost approach both assume that nature’s value is not immediately affected as it is used. As such, they classify nature as an asset. Given the different classifications of nature, the biodiversity accounting approaches also promote different values of nature. According to Unai and et al. (2022) nature can have three types of values: instrumental (nature as an asset or resource valued for its contributions to people’s well-being), intrinsic (nature valued in its own right as an end in itself), or relational (value located in human-nature interactions such as via sense of place and belonging, stewardship and reciprocity). Table 6 again shows how the three accounting approaches promote these values.

Given the noted characteristics (motivation, foci, classification, and values of nature), the three biodiversity accounting approaches have different underpinning accounting logics. The ecosystem

and largely also the inventory approach put humans' interests at the center in that they assume that we can readily use natural resources for our benefit. They thus operate based on an anthropocentric accounting logic (Bebbington et al., 2020). In comparison, the cost approach – and to some extent also the inventory approach (see invaluable stock) – ascribes an intrinsic value to all living things on earth and recognizes the interdependence between those things. This approach thus adopts a non-anthropocentric accounting logic.

EU biodiversity accounting approaches and logics

Building on the above synthesis, Table 7 summarizes our findings on the accounting approaches adopted by the EU's corporate disclosure framework for biodiversity (put forward by the three key legislative texts SFDR, TR, and CSRD/ESRS).

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	CSRD/ESRS	Taxonomy Regulation	SFDR	
Key terms and definitions	biodiversity	The variability among living organisms from all sources including, inter alia, terrestrial, freshwater, marine and other aquatic ecosystems and the ecological complexes of which they are part.(UN, 1992)	The variability among living organisms arising from all sources including terrestrial, marine and other aquatic ecosystems and the ecological complexes of which they are part and includes diversity within species, between species and of ecosystems. (UN, 1992)	N/A
	ecosystem	A dynamic complex of plant, animal and micro-organism communities and their non-living environment interacting as a functional unit. A typology of ecosystems is provided by the IUCN Global Ecosystem Typology 2.0.	A dynamic complex of plant, animal, and micro-organism communities and their non-living environment interacting as a functional unit.	N/A
	ecosystem services	The contributions of ecosystems to the benefits that are used in economic and other human activity, respectively the benefits people obtain from ecosystems. In the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, ecosystem services can be divided into supporting, regulating, provisioning and cultural. The Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services (CICES) classifies types of ecosystems services.	The direct and indirect contributions of ecosystems to the economic, social, cultural and other benefits that people derive from those ecosystems	N/A
	habitat	The place or type of site where an organism or population naturally occurs. Also used to mean the environmental attributes required by a particular species or its ecological niche.	N/A	N/A
	impacts	The effect the undertaking has or could have on the environment and people, including effects on their human rights, as a result of the undertaking's activities or business relationships. The impacts can be actual or potential, negative or positive, short-term or long-term time horizons, intended or unintended, and reversible or irreversible. Impacts indicate the undertaking's contribution, negative or positive, to sustainable development.	N/A	N/A
	dependencies	Dependency is the result of the undertaking relying on biodiversity and/or ecosystems within its business model and/or conduct of business.	N/A	N/A
	risks	Uncertain environmental, social or governance events or conditions that, if they occur, could cause a potential material negative effect on the undertaking's business model, strategy and sustainability strategy, its capability to achieve its goals and targets and to create value, and therefore may influence its decisions and those of its business relationships with regard to sustainability matters. Like any other risks, sustainability related risks are the combination of an impact's magnitude and the probability of occurrence.	N/A	An environmental, social or governance event or condition that, if it occurs, could cause an actual or a potential material negative impact on the value of the investment;
	opportunities	Uncertain environmental, social or governance events or conditions that, if they occur, could cause a potential material positive effect on the undertaking's business model, strategy, its capability to achieve its goals and targets and to create value, and therefore may influence its decisions and those of its business relationship partners with regards to sustainability matters. Like any other opportunity, sustainability-related opportunities are measured as a combination of an impact's magnitude and the probability of occurrence.	N/A	N/A
	materiality	A sustainability matter is material if it meets the definition of impact materiality, financial materiality, or both. A sustainability matter is	N/A	N/A

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	CSRD/ESRS	Taxonomy Regulation	SFDR	
	material from a financial perspective if it generates risks or opportunities that affect (or could reasonably be expected to affect) the undertaking's financial position, financial performance, cash flows, access to finance or cost of capital over the short, medium or long term. A sustainability matter is material from an impact perspective when it pertains to the undertaking's material actual or potential, positive or negative impacts on people or the environment over the short-, medium- and long-term. A material sustainability matter from an impact perspective includes impacts connected with the undertaking's own operations and upstream and downstream value chain, including through its products and services, as well as through its business relationships.			
Assessment and disclosure requirements	assessment and disclosure level	Entity level (parent & subsidiary)	Activity and entity level	
	assessment focus	dependencies, impacts, risks, and opportunities	dependencies, impacts, risks, and opportunities	
	assessment approach	LEAP approach: 1. Locate your interface with nature in your value chain 2. Evaluate your dependencies and impacts on nature 3. Assess your nature-related risks and opportunities 4. Prepare to respond to, and report on, material nature-related issues, aligned with the ESRS	Three step classification process: 1. Activity significantly contributes to at least one environmental objective; 2. Activity does no significant harm to any of the other five environmental objectives; 3. Activity complies with minimum social safeguards	Three step classification process: 1. Does the fund have sustainable investment as its objective (Taxonomy aligned)? 2. Does the fund promote environmental and/or social characteristics? 3. Does the fund not promote environmental and/or social characteristics?
	disclosure basis	Materiality	TSC thresholds, and DNSH criteria as well as MMS	TSC thresholds, and DNSH criteria as well as MMS
	disclosure structure	Four-pillars	Six pillars	Three categories
	disclosure content	_Governance, _Strategy _Management of impacts, risks and opportunities _Metrics and targets	proportionality of taxonomy aligned activities in six environmental objectives: 1. climate change mitigation, 2. climate change adaptation, 3. sustainable use and protection of water and marine resources, 4. transition to a circular economy, 5. pollution prevention and control, 6. protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems	Proportionality of products as in _Article 6 _Article 8 _Article 9
	disclosure types	Qualitative and quantitative	Qualitative, quantitative, monetary	Qualitative, quantitative, monetary
	accounting approach	Natural inventory, ecosystem, cost (through recognition of nature risks)	Natural inventory, ecosystem, cost (through climate risk analysis)	Cost
	connection to other frameworks	EU Taxonomy, CSRD, TNFD	SFDR, Green bond standard	EU Taxonomy, CSRD, ESRS
	sector guidance (y/n)	Draft	Yes	Yes
	sector guidance	_Oil and Gas _Coal, Quarries and Mining _Road Transport	Financial and non-financial undertakings	Financial undertakings

	CSRD/ESRS	Taxonomy Regulation	SFDR
	_Agriculture, Farming and Fisheries _Motor Vehicles _Energy Production and Utilities _Food and Beverages _Textiles, Accessories, Footwear and Jewellery		
scope of value chain	Direct operations, upstream and downstream (In case there are associates or joint ventures (within equity method or proportionally consolidated) that are involved in the value chain (supplier) then this should be included in the report)	N/A	N/A

Table 7: Overview of the EU's corporate disclosure framework for biodiversity

EU biodiversity indicators and metrics

Following the analysis of the EU's corporate disclosure framework for biodiversity, we also analyzed the key biodiversity indicators and metrics put forward in this framework. Appendix 2b presents a full summary of this analysis, as well as a comparison of the EU's indicators and metrics to those of the three other most important corporate disclosure frameworks globally (the TNFD, the GRI and the ISSB). While this comparative analysis yielded many interesting aspects, below we summarize **three key observations**.

First, a large proportion of the EU's biodiversity indicators and metrics **focus on biodiversity loss driver minimization and the protection of nature**. The main biodiversity loss drivers addressed by the EU's biodiversity indicators and metrics are **climate change and pollution**. The focus of nature protection is on **ecosystems and species**. As such, this is in line with the EU's policy focus. Yet, comparing this focus with the indicators and metrics of the other main disclosure frameworks, differences emerge. The indicators and metrics put forward by the ESRS, the GRI, and the ISSB all focus on the biodiversity loss drivers of climate change and pollution. A large proportion of their indicators and metrics focus, for example, on the reduction of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and the reduction of waste (focusing for instance on plastic and the fostering of circularity of products). However, the indicators and metrics put forward by the TNFD focus on the biodiversity loss driver and sea and land use change. Notably, the TNFD was the only disclosure framework that put forward comprehensive indicators that capture fresh-water and ocean drainage. The GRI, with an emphasis on habitat fragmentation, is more aligned with the TNFD. Table 8 highlights these foci, also demonstrating the limited coverage of the EU's indicators and metrics.

	Indicator	Metric	TNFD	GRI	ESRS	Taxonomy	SFDR	ISSB
Land/Water/Sea use change Land conversion & deforestation	Total Spatial Footprint	Sum of: total surface area controlled/managed by organisation (km ²); Total disturbed area (km ²); and total rehabilitated/restored area (km ²)	Yes (C)		Yes (V - Total use of land area)			
	Extent of land-use change	land-use change (Km ²) by ecosystem (i.e., realm)	Yes (C)	Yes (I01-6, size (ha) of land converted from one intensively used or modified ecosystem to another during reporting period, and type of				

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Indicator	Metric	TNFD	GRI	ESRS	Taxonomy	SFDR	ISSB
			ecosystem before and after conversion)				
Extent of land-use change	size (ha) of natural ecosystem converted since a cut-off date, and type of ecosystem before and after conversion		Yes (101-6)				
Extent of land-use change	land-use change (Km2) by business activity	Yes (C)		Yes (V - narrative, conversion over time of land cover (e.g. deforestation, mining)			
Extent of land-use change	land voluntarily conserved or restored (Km2)	Yes (C)	Yes (V-101-6, % of sourced supply chain product volume that is conversion or deforestation free)				
Extent of land-use change	land required to be conserved or restored (Km2)	Yes (C)					
Extent of land-use change	land sustainably managed (Km2) by ecosystem (ie realm)	Yes (C)					
Extent of land-use change	land sustainably managed (Km2) by business activity	Yes (C)					
Intensity of land-use	land use intensity (t or litres of output/km2)	Yes (A)					
Intensity of land-use	land-use based on Life Cycle Assessment			Yes (V - narrative)			
Intensity of land-use	Total sealed land area			Yes (V - Area)			
freshwater conversion & drainage	Total Spatial Footprint	Sum of: total surface area controlled/managed by organisation (km2); Total disturbed area (km2); and total rehabilitated/restored area (km2)	Yes (C)				
	Extent of freshwater use change	freshwater use change by ecosystem (i.e., realm)	Yes (C)				
	Extent of freshwater use change	freshwater use change by business activity	Yes (C)				
	Extent of freshwater use change	freshwater voluntarily conserved or restored	Yes (C)				
	Extent of freshwater use change	freshwater required to be conserved or restored	Yes (C)				
	Extent of freshwater use change	freshwater sustainably managed (Km2) by ecosystem (ie realm)	Yes (C)				
	Extent of freshwater use change	freshwater sustainably managed (Km2) by business activity	Yes (C)				
ocean	Total Spatial Footprint	Sum of: total surface area controlled/managed by organisation	Yes (C)				

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Indicator	Metric	TNFD	GRI	ESRS	Taxonomy	SFDR	ISSB
	(km2); Total disturbed area (km2); and total rehabilitated/restored area (km2)						
Extent of ocean use change	ocean use change by ecosystem (i.e., realm)	Yes (C)	Yes (101-6, size (ha) of sea converted from one intensively used or modified ecosystem to another during reporting period, and type of ecosystem before and after conversion)				
Extent of ocean use change	ocean use change by business activity	Yes (C)					
Extent of ocean use change	ocean voluntarily conserved or restored	Yes (C)					
Extent of ocean use change	ocean required to be conserved or restored	Yes (C)					
Extent of ocean use change	ocean sustainably managed (Km2) by ecosystem (i.e., realm)	Yes (C)					
Extent of ocean use change	ocean sustainably managed (Km2) by business activity	Yes (C)					
Extent of ecosystem use change	ecosystem use change by ecosystem (i.e., realm)	Yes (C)					
Extent of ecosystem use change	ecosystem use change by business activity	Yes (C)	Yes (101-5, activities that take place in areas per site)	Yes (semi-narrative, Activities related to sites located in or near biodiversity-sensitive areas negatively affect these areas by leading to deterioration of natural habitats and habitats of species and to disturbance of species for which protected area has been designated. And activities related to sites located in or near biodiversity-sensitive areas negatively affect these areas where conclusions or necessary mitigation measures have not been implemented or are ongoing)		Yes	
habitat fragmentation	Extent of ecosystem use change	ecosystem voluntarily conserved or restored	Yes (C)				
	Extent of ecosystem use change	ecosystem required to be conserved or restored	Yes (C)				

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Indicator	Metric	TNFD	GRI	ESRS	Taxonomy	SFDR	ISSB
Extent of ecosystem use change	ecosystem sustainably managed (Km2) by ecosystem (i.e., realm)	Yes (C)					
Extent of ecosystem use change	ecosystem sustainably managed (Km2) by business activity	Yes (C)		Yes (V-narrative, changes over time in management of ecosystem (e.g., through intensification of agricultural management, or application of better management practices))			
Impact on ecologically sensitive areas	Number of sites owned, leased or managed in or near protected areas or key biodiversity areas that undertaking is negatively affecting		Yes (101-2, 101-7)	Yes (narrative, biodiversity-sensitive areas impacted)			
Impact on ecologically sensitive areas	Area of sites owned, leased or managed in or near protected areas or key biodiversity areas that undertaking is negatively affecting		Yes (101-2, ha)	Yes (Area)			
Impact on ecologically sensitive areas	Material sites located in or near ecologically sensitive area		Yes (101-2, 101-5, location and size (in ha) of sites)	Yes (semi-narrative, V - Area of nature-oriented area on and off site)			
Impact on ecologically sensitive areas	% of sites (relative to total number of sites) in or near ecologically sensitive areas		Yes (101-5)				
Impact on ecologically sensitive areas	distance of each material site to ecologically sensitive areas		Yes (V - 101-5 - only if site is near area)				
Impact on ecologically sensitive areas	areas of high ecosystem integrity per material site		Yes (101-5)				
Impact on ecologically sensitive areas	areas of rapid decline in ecosystem integrity per material site		Yes (101-5)				
Impact on ecologically sensitive areas	areas of high physical water risks per material site		Yes (101-5)				
Extent of ecosystem use change	countries or jurisdictions where activities associated with products/services with most significant biodiversity impact take place		Yes (101-5)				
Extent of ecosystem use change	whether the key biodiversity action is intended to be a one-time initiative or systematic practice	Yes (A, duration (years) of ecosystem restoration and/or species restoration projects, and duration (years) of	Yes similar (101-2, but it only covers offset actions)	Yes (V - narrative)			

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Indicator	Metric	TNFD	GRI	ESRS	Taxonomy	SFDR	ISSB
		voluntary ecosystem and/or species restoration projects)					
Impact on ecologically sensitive areas	Activities related to sites located in or near biodiversity-sensitive areas negatively affect these areas where conclusions or necessary mitigation measures have not been implemented are ongoing		Yes (101-5)	Yes (narrative)		Yes (narrative)	
Impact on ecologically sensitive areas	Activities related to sites located in or near biodiversity-sensitive areas negatively affect these areas by leading to deterioration of natural habitats and habitats of species and to disturbance of species for which protected area has been designated		Yes (101-5)	Yes (semi-narrative)			
Impact on ecologically sensitive areas	Key biodiversity and ecosystem action may induce significant negative sustainability impacts			Yes (V - narrative)			
Extent of ecosystem use change	extent of (km3) restoration of negatively affected species and ecosystems by ecosystem (realm) required by regulation	Yes (A)					
Extent of ecosystem use change	extent of (km3) restoration of negatively affected species and ecosystems by ecosystem (realm) required by certifier	Yes (A)					
Extent of ecosystem use change	extent of (km3) restoration of negatively affected species and ecosystems by ecosystem (realm) and voluntarily	Yes (A)					
Extent of ecosystem use change	extent of (km3) restoration of negatively affected species and ecosystems by biome required by regulation	Yes (A)					
Extent of ecosystem use change	extent of (km3) restoration of negatively affected species and ecosystems by biome required by certifier	Yes (A)					
Extent of ecosystem use change	extent of (km3) restoration of negatively affected species and ecosystems by biome and voluntarily	Yes (A)					
Extent of ecosystem use change	extent (km3) of ecosystem restoration and/or species restoration projects	Yes (A)	Yes similar (101-2, size of area (in ha) under restoration or rehabilitated per site with most impact on biodiversity)				

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Indicator	Metric	TNFD	GRI	ESRS	Taxonomy	SFDR	ISSB
Extent of ecosystem use change	monitoring frequency (count/year) of ecosystem restoration and/or species restoration projects	Yes (A)					
Extent of ecosystem use change	extent (km3) of voluntary ecosystem and/or species restoration projects	Yes (A)	could be covered in 101-2				
Extent of ecosystem use change	monitoring frequency (count/year) of voluntary ecosystem and/or species restoration projects	Yes (A)					

Table 8: Indicators and metrics for land-and-sea-use change

(C) refers to core indicators of the TNFD, whereas (A) refers to additional indicators of the TNFD.
V refers to voluntary indicators of the GRI and the ESRS.

Second, the EU's biodiversity indicators and metrics **focus on financial risks and opportunities, notably physical financial risks** (see table 9). As such, attention to financial effects of biodiversity loss focuses on enabling the provision of better financing. The indicators and metrics thus also cover the financing policy focus of the EU. The comparison to other disclosure frameworks further reveals that most of them share the call for attention to financial effects of biodiversity loss. Notably, a large proportion of the TNFD's indicators and metrics also focuses on financial risks and opportunities, and there is also a major focus on physical financial risks. However, while the EU specifies few indicators on financial transition risks (related to e.g., the energy transition), the TNFD also emphasizes the necessity to understand these risks in relation to biodiversity loss. In line with its impact-only approach (see table 7), the GRI only puts forward a few indicators and metrics related to financial opportunities (coming from its non-biodiversity standards).

	Indicator	Metric	TNFD	GRI	ESRS	Taxonomy	SFDR	ISSB
transition risk	assets	Total value of assets that are vulnerable to nature-related transition risks	Yes (C)					
	assets	% of total value of assets that are vulnerable to nature-related transition risks	Yes (C)					
	assets	Total value of assets that are vulnerable to climate-related transition risks	Yes (C)					Yes
	assets	% of total value of assets that are vulnerable to climate-related transition risks	Yes (C)		Yes (E1)			Yes
	liabilities	Total value of liabilities that are vulnerable to nature-related transition risks	Yes (C)					
	liabilities	% of total value of liabilities that are vulnerable to nature-related transition risks	Yes (C)					
	income	Total value of revenue that is vulnerable to nature-related transition risks	Yes (C)					

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Indicator	Metric	TNFD	GRI	ESRS	Taxonomy	SFDR	ISSB
income	% of total value of revenue that is vulnerable to nature-related transition risks	Yes (C)					
income	Total value of expenses that are vulnerable to nature-related transition risks	Yes (C)					
income	% of total value of expenses that are vulnerable to nature-related transition risks	Yes (C)					
assets	total value of assets exposed to nature-related transition risks	Yes (A)					
assets	% value of assets (from total) exposed to nature-related transition risks	Yes (A)					
liabilities	total value of liabilities exposed to nature-related transition risks	Yes (A)					
liabilities	% value of liabilities (from total) exposed to nature-related transition risks	Yes (A)					
income	total value of revenue exposed to nature-related transition risks	Yes (A)					
income	% value of revenue (from total) exposed to nature-related transition risks	Yes (A)					
income	total value of expenses exposed to nature-related transition risks	Yes (A)					
income	% value of expenses (from total) exposed to nature-related transition risks	Yes (A)					
income	description of loss of operating areas	Yes (A)		Yes (E5 - narrative; Material impacts and risks of staying in business as usual)			
income	costs related to loss of operating areas	Yes (A)					
income	description of clean-up costs due to nature-related impacts	Yes (A)					
income	value of clean-up costs due to nature-related impacts	Yes (A)					
market	description of exposure to loss of market access	Yes (A)					
market	costs related to loss of market access	Yes (A)					
market	description of exposure to raw material and natural resource price volatility	Yes (A)					
market	costs related to raw material and natural resource price volatility	Yes (A)					
technology	R&D expenditure for new and alternative technologies related to	Yes (A)					

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Indicator	Metric	TNFD	GRI	ESRS	Taxonomy	SFDR	ISSB
	mitigation and adaption of nature-related risks						
	market	Material impacts and risks of transition to circular economy		Yes (E5 - narrative)			
Reputational risks		exposure to increase operational costs due to reputational risks	Yes (A)				
		loss of revenue due to reputational risks	Yes (A)				
physical risk	assets	Total value of assets that are vulnerable to nature-related physical risks	Yes (C)	Yes (information about potential financial effects of material risks arising from biodiversity- and ecosystem-related impacts and dependencies, also narrative)			
	assets	% of total value of assets that are vulnerable to nature-related physical risks	Yes (C)	Yes could be (monetary, potential financial effects of material risks and opportunities arising from biodiversity- and ecosystem-related impacts and dependencies)			
	assets	Total value of assets that are vulnerable to climate-related physical risks	Yes (C)	Yes (E1, estimated amount of potentially stranded assets)			Yes
	assets	% of total value of assets that are vulnerable to climate-related physical risks	Yes (C)	Yes could be (monetary, potential financial effects of material risks and opportunities arising from biodiversity- and ecosystem-related impacts and dependencies)			Yes
	liabilities	Total value of liabilities that are vulnerable to nature-related physical risks	Yes (C)	Yes (information about potential financial effects of material risks arising from biodiversity- and ecosystem-related impacts and dependencies, also narrative)			
	liabilities	% of total value of liabilities that are vulnerable to nature-related physical risks	Yes (C)	Yes could be (monetary, potential financial effects of material risks and opportunities arising from biodiversity- and ecosystem-related impacts and dependencies)			
	income	Total value of revenue that is vulnerable to nature-related physical risks	Yes (C)	Yes could be (monetary, potential financial effects of			

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Indicator	Metric	TNFD	GRI	ESRS	Taxonomy	SFDR	ISSB
				material risks and opportunities arising from biodiversity- and ecosystem-related impacts and dependencies)			
income	% of total value of revenue that is vulnerable to nature-related physical risks	Yes (C)		Yes could be (monetary, potential financial effects of material risks and opportunities arising from biodiversity- and ecosystem-related impacts and dependencies)			
income	Total value of expenses that are vulnerable to nature-related physical risks	Yes (C)		Yes could be (monetary, potential financial effects of material risks and opportunities arising from biodiversity- and ecosystem-related impacts and dependencies)			
income	% of total value of expenses that are vulnerable to nature-related physical risks	Yes (C)		Yes could be (monetary, potential financial effects of material risks and opportunities arising from biodiversity- and ecosystem-related impacts and dependencies)			
assets	value of assets dependent on area affected by physical risk	Yes (A)		Yes could be (monetary, potential financial effects of material risks and opportunities arising from biodiversity- and ecosystem-related impacts and dependencies)			
income	value of total annual revenue dependent on area affected by physical risk	Yes (A)		Yes could be (monetary, potential financial effects of material risks and opportunities arising from biodiversity- and ecosystem-related impacts and dependencies)			
sites	number of locations/business lines/facilities exposed to physical risk	Yes (A)					

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Indicator	Metric	TNFD	GRI	ESRS	Taxonomy	SFDR	ISSB
assets	value of CapEx on infrastructure asset repair or replacement as a result of nature-related loss and damage	Yes (A)		Yes could be (monetary, potential financial effects of material risks and opportunities arising from biodiversity- and ecosystem-related impacts and dependencies)			
income	% increase in insurance costs due to nature-related loss and damage in the previous year	Yes (A)		Yes could be (monetary, potential financial effects of material risks and opportunities arising from biodiversity- and ecosystem-related impacts and dependencies)			
income	CapEx on adaption due to nature-related physical risks	Yes (A)		Yes could be (monetary, potential financial effects of material risks and opportunities arising from biodiversity- and ecosystem-related impacts and dependencies)			
income	value of CapEx, financing or investment deployed towards nature-related risks	Yes (A)		Yes could be (monetary, potential financial effects of material risks and opportunities arising from biodiversity- and ecosystem-related impacts and dependencies)			
income	total costs associated with the relocation of operations and suppliers due to physical risks	Yes (A)		Yes could be (monetary, potential financial effects of material risks and opportunities arising from biodiversity- and ecosystem-related impacts and dependencies)			
income	% of costs (from total) associated with the relocation of operations and suppliers due to physical risks	Yes (A)		Yes could be (monetary, potential financial effects of material risks and opportunities arising from biodiversity- and ecosystem-related impacts and dependencies)			

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Indicator	Metric	TNFD	GRI	ESRS	Taxonomy	SFDR	ISSB
	value of write-offs and early retirements of assets due to nature-related risks	Yes (A)		Yes could be (monetary, potential financial effects of material risks and opportunities arising from biodiversity- and ecosystem-related impacts and dependencies)			
income	Net revenue from activities in high climate impact sectors			Yes (V - E1, E2, E3)			
income	Net revenue from activities other than in high climate impact sectors			Yes (V - E1)			
income	total GHG emissions per net revenue(location-based)		Yes (305-4)	Yes (V - E1)		Yes (E1)	
income	total GHG emissions per net revenue (market-based)		Yes (305-4)	Yes (E1)		Yes (E1)	
products	related products and services at risk (biodiversity and ecosystems) over the short-, medium- and long-term			Yes (V - narrative)			
liabilities	Provisions for environmental protection and remediation costs			Yes (E2)			
financed emissions	absolute gross financed emissions by scope	Yes (C - for asset management, commercial banking & insurance (for both by industry and asset class))					Yes (for asset management, commercial banking & insurance (for both by industry and asset class))
financed emissions	total AUM for each scope financed emissions in currency of financial statements	Yes (C, for asset management)					Yes (for asset management)
financed emissions	percentage of total AUM in financed emissions calculation	Yes (C, for asset management)					Yes (for asset management)
financed emissions	gross exposure of funded carrying amounts to industries by asset class in currency of financial statements	Yes (C, for commercial banking & insurance)					Yes (for commercial banking & insurance)
financed emissions	gross exposure of undrawn loan commitments to industries by asset class in currency of financial statements	Yes (C, for commercial banking & insurance)					Yes (for commercial banking & insurance)
financed emissions	percentage of entity's gross exposure included in financed emissions calculation	Yes (C, for commercial banking & insurance)					Yes (for commercial banking & insurance)

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Indicator	Metric	TNFD	GRI	ESRS	Taxonomy	SFDR	ISSB
technology	R&D expenditure for new and alternative technologies related to mitigation and adaption of nature-related risks	Yes (A)					
societal	whether and how systemic risks to society have been considered in assessment of biodiversity and ecosystems-related risks			Yes (narrative)			
other	Explanation of relationship of significant CapEx and OpEx required to implement actions taken or planned to key performance indicators required under Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2021/2178			Yes (E1 - narrative)			
other	Relationship of significant CapEx and OpEx required to implement actions taken or planned to CapEx plan required by Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2021/2178			Yes (E1 - narrative)			
other	Potential differences between significant OpEx and CapEx disclosed under ESRS E1 and key performance indicators disclosed under Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2021/2178			Yes (E1 - narrative)			
other	Principle Adverse Impacts of investments					Yes	
fines	value of significant fines/penalties received/litigation action in the year due to negative nature-related risks an opportunities	Yes (C)					
	description of significant fines/penalties received/litigation action in the year due to negative nature-related risks an opportunities	Yes (C)					

Table 9: Indicators and metrics for (biodiversity-related) financial risks

(C) refers to core indicators of the TNFD, whereas (A) refers to additional indicators of the TNFD.

V refers to voluntary indicators of the GRI and the ESRS.

The **third** noteworthy observation is that the EU's biodiversity indicators and metrics **focus to a large extent on corporate governance**. Numerous indicators and metrics, for example, concern corporate **biodiversity action, policies, and targets**. Further, since most of these indicators and metrics are labelled as minimum disclosure requirement (MDR) under ESRS2, the EU emphasizes the centrality of good and fair decision-making processes for the tackling of biodiversity loss. This is broadly in line with its policy focus area, albeit to an unbalanced degree as there are unproportionally many governance indicators

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and metrics in the ESRS (vis a vis governance only covering 10% of the EU's policy focus). Comparing this governance focus to other disclosure frameworks, there is, overall, large alignment. However, this primarily relates to the indicators and metrics regarding the disclosure on defined biodiversity targets (all disclosure frameworks propose similar indicators on science-based targets). There is less consensus regarding the indicators and metrics for biodiversity actions (notably those on the mitigation hierarchy) and policies (see table 10 below). The GRI and the ESRS, for example, outline many indicators and metrics on both biodiversity actions and policies. In comparison, the TNFD defines few of these.

In addition to the differences regarding indicators and metrics on biodiversity policies and actions, there is some misalignment regarding the disclosure of measurement assumptions (see table 10). The ESRS and GRI define a couple of indicators and metrics on impact assessment assumptions (notably regarding assessment scenarios chosen). In comparison, the TNFD outlines relatively little of these. Instead, it focuses on indicators and metrics in relation to value chain inclusion/assessment. Lastly, while the GRI and ESRS put forward a few indicators and metrics regarding the inclusion of indigenous peoples and their knowledge, the TNFD (or ISSB) do not mention such indicators and metrics.

Indicator	Metric	TNFD	GRI	ESRS	Taxonomy	SFDR	ISSB
transition plan	Explanation of how business strategy interacts with transition plan		Yes (V-101-2, how organisation ensures that business model compatible with transition to halt biodiversity loss)	Yes (V - narrative)			
transition plan	Explanation of investments and funding supporting the implementation of its transition plan			Yes (V - narrative)			
transition plan	Administrative, management and supervisory bodies have approved transition plan		Yes (V - narrative)	Yes (V - narrative)			
transition plan	Information about how process of implementing and updating transition plan is managed	Yes (C)		Yes (V - narrative)			Yes
transition plan	Investments and funding supporting the implementation of its transition plan			Yes (V)			
transition plan	Biodiversity offsets are part of transition plan		Yes (101-2)	Yes (V - narrative)			
transition plan	Transition plan to improve and achieve alignment of its business model and value chain			Yes (narrative)			
policies overview	Current challenges and limitations to draft plan in relation to areas of significant impact and actions company is taking to address them (biodiversity and ecosystems)			Yes (V - narrative)			
policies overview	Description of key contents of policy related to manage material impacts, risks, dependencies and opportunities related to biodiversity and ecosystems		Yes (101-1)	Yes (ESRS 2 MDR P - narrative)			
policies overview	Scope of policy related to manage material impacts, risks, dependencies and		Yes (V-101-1)	Yes (ESRS 2 MDR P - narrative)			

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Indicator	Metric	TNFD	GRI	ESRS	Taxonomy	SFDR	ISSB
	opportunities related to biodiversity and ecosystems or of its exclusions						
accountability	Most senior level in organisation that is accountable for implementation of policy related to manage material impacts, risks, dependencies and opportunities related to biodiversity and ecosystems			Yes (ESRS 2 MDR P - narrative)			
policies overview	Third-party standards or initiatives that are respected through implementation of policy related to manage material impacts, risks, dependencies and opportunities related to biodiversity and ecosystems		Yes (101-2)	Yes (ESRS 2 MDR P - narrative)			
policies overview	Reasons for not having adopted policy related to manage material impacts, risks, dependencies and opportunities related to biodiversity and ecosystems		Yes (101-1)	Yes (ESRS 2 MDR P - narrative)			
policies overview	Timeframe in which the undertakings aim to adopt policy related to manage material impacts, risks, dependencies and opportunities related to biodiversity and ecosystems		Yes (101-1)	Yes (ESRS 2 MDR P - V - narrative)			
policy contributions	whether and how biodiversity and ecosystems-related policies relate to matters reported in E4 AR4			Yes (narrative)			
policy contributions	whether and how biodiversity and ecosystems-related policy relates to material biodiversity and ecosystems-related impacts		Yes (V - 101-1)	Yes (narrative)			
policy contributions	whether and how biodiversity and ecosystems-related policy relates to material dependencies and material physical and transition risks and opportunities			Yes (narrative)			
policy traceability	whether and how biodiversity and ecosystems-related policy supports traceability of products, components and raw materials with significant actual or potential impacts on biodiversity and ecosystems along value chain		Yes similar (101-2, traceability mechanisms used to identify origin of products and entities in supply chain, including actions to improve traceability)	Yes (narrative)			
policy contributions	whether and how biodiversity and ecosystems-related policy addresses production, sourcing or consumption from ecosystems that are managed to maintain or enhance conditions for biodiversity			Yes (narrative)			
policy contributions	whether and how biodiversity and ecosystems-related policy addresses social			Yes (narrative)			

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Indicator	Metric	TNFD	GRI	ESRS	Taxonomy	SFDR	ISSB
	consequences of biodiversity and ecosystems-related impacts						
policies overview	how policy refers to production, sourcing or consumption of raw materials			Yes (V - narrative)			
policies overview	how policy refers to policies limiting procurement from suppliers that cannot demonstrate that they are not contributing to significant conversion of protected areas or key biodiversity areas			Yes (V - narrative)			
policies overview	how policy refers to recognised standards or third-party certifications overseen by regulators			Yes (V - narrative)			
policy contributions	how policy addresses raw materials originating from ecosystems that have been managed to maintain or enhance conditions for biodiversity, as demonstrated by regular monitoring and reporting of biodiversity status and gains or losses			Yes (V - narrative)			
policy assurance	Third-party standard of conduct used in policy is objective and achievable based on scientific approach to identifying issues and realistic in assessing how these issues can be addressed under variety of practical circumstances		Yes (I01-1)	Yes (V - semi-narrative)			
policy assurance	Third-party standard of conduct used in policy encourages stepwise approach and continuous improvement in standard and its application of better management practices and requires establishment of meaningful targets and specific milestones to indicate progress against principles and criteria over time		Yes (I01-2)	Yes (V - semi-narrative)			
policy assurance	Third-party standard of conduct used in policy is verifiable through independent certifying or verifying bodies, which have defined and rigorous assessment procedures that avoid conflicts of interest and are compliant with ISO guidance on accreditation and verification procedures or Article 5(2) of Regulation (EC) No 765/2008			Yes (V - semi-narrative)			
policy assurance	Third-party standard of conduct used in policy conforms to ISEAL Code of Good Practice			Yes (V - semi-narrative)			
policies overview	Biodiversity and ecosystem protection policy covering operational sites owned, leased, managed in or near protected area			Yes (semi-narrative)			

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Indicator	Metric	TNFD	GRI	ESRS	Taxonomy	SFDR	ISSB
	or biodiversity-sensitive area outside protected areas has been adopted						
policies overview	Sustainable land or agriculture practices or policies have been adopted			Yes (semi-narrative)		Yes	
policies overview	Sustainable oceans or seas practices or policies have been adopted			Yes (semi-narrative)		Yes	
policies overview	Policies to address deforestation have been adopted			Yes (semi-narrative)		Yes	
policy contributions	Disclosure of contextual information on relations between policies implemented and how policies contribute to EU Action Plan Towards Zero Pollution for Air, Water and Soil			Yes (E2 - V- narrative)			
policy contributions	how policies or commitments to halt and reverse biodiversity loss are informed by the 2050 Goals and 2030 Targets in the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework		Yes (101-1)				
accountability	explanation whether business relationships are obligated to abide by the policies or commitments or are only encouraged to do so		Yes (101-1)				
accountability	how responsibility to ensure access and benefit sharing regulation compliance is allocated		Yes (101-3)				
policies overview	how access and benefit sharing regulations are integrated into strategies, operational policies and operational procedures		Yes (101-3)				
policies overview	what training is provided on implementing access and benefit sharing regulations and measures		Yes (101-3)				
accountability	whether and how climate related considerations factored into executive remuneration	Yes (C)					Yes
accountability	percentage of executive management remuneration recognised in current period that is linked to climate related considerations	Yes (C)					Yes
business model	Business model(s) has been verified using range of biodiversity and ecosystems scenarios, or other scenarios with modelling of biodiversity and ecosystems related consequences, with different possible pathways			Yes (V - narrative)			
business model	Explanation of how strategy and business model will be adjusted to improve and,			Yes (narrative)			

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Indicator	Metric	TNFD	GRI	ESRS	Taxonomy	SFDR	ISSB
	ultimately, achieve alignment with relevant local, national and global public policy goals						
policies overview	Disclosure of objectives or plans for aligning economic activities (revenues, CapEx)			Yes (V - narrative)			
policies overview	whether and how carbon pricing is applied in decision-making	Yes (C)					Yes
business model	resilience of current business model(s) and strategy to biodiversity and ecosystems-related physical, transition and systemic risks and opportunities			Yes (narrative)			
business model	results of resilience analysis (biodiversity and ecosystems)			Yes (narrative)			
actions overview	% of sites producing and effectively implementing nature action plans	Yes (A)	Yes (101-2, list of sites adopting action plans)				
actions overview	Key actions taken related to biodiversity and ecosystems		Yes (101-2, actions on site and organisational level and in both supply and value chain)	Yes (ESRS 2 MDR A - narrative)			
actions overview	Scope of key action related to biodiversity and ecosystems		Yes (101-2)	Yes (ESRS 2 MDR A - narrative)			
actions overview	Time horizon under which key action related to biodiversity and ecosystems is to be completed		Yes (101-2)	Yes (ESRS 2 MDR A - semi-narrative)			
actions overview	Key action related to biodiversity and ecosystems taken, and its results, to provide for and cooperate in or support provision of remedy for those harmed by actual material impacts		Yes similar (101-2, explanations if an organisation avoids activities in or near ecologically sensitive areas)	Yes (ESRS 2 MDR A - narrative)			
actions overview	Quantitative and qualitative information regarding progress of action related to biodiversity and ecosystems or action plans disclosed in prior periods			Yes (ESRS 2 MDR A - narrative)			
action investments	Type of current and future financial and other resources allocated to the action plan related to biodiversity and ecosystems			Yes (ESRS 2 MDR A - narrative)			
action investments	Current financial resources allocated to action plan related to biodiversity and ecosystems plan (Capex)			Yes (ESRS 2 MDR A - monetary)	Yes		
action investments	Current financial resources allocated to action plan related to biodiversity and ecosystems plan (Opex)			Yes (ESRS 2 MDR A - monetary)	Yes		
action investments	Future financial resources allocated to action plan related to biodiversity and ecosystems (Capex)			Yes (ESRS 2 MDR A - monetary)			
action investments	Future financial resources allocated to action plan related to biodiversity and ecosystems (Opex)			Yes (ESRS 2 MDR A - monetary)			

Actions

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Indicator	Metric	TNFD	GRI	ESRS	Taxonomy	SFDR	ISSB
actions overview	Reasons for not having adopted actions related to biodiversity and ecosystems		Yes (101-2)	Yes (ESRS 2 MDR A - narrative)			
actions overview	Timeframe in which the undertakings aim to adopt action related to biodiversity and ecosystems		Yes (101-2)	Yes (ESRS 2 MDR A - V - narrative)			
actions mitigation hierarchy relation	How the mitigation hierarchy has been applied with regard to biodiversity and ecosystem actions		Yes similar (101-2, how mitigation hierarchy is applied: actions to avoid negative impacts, actions to minimise negative impacts that were not avoided, actions taken to restore and rehabilitate affected ecosystems, actions taken to offset residual negative impact, transformative actions and conservation actions)	Yes (V - narrative)			
actions mitigation hierarchy relation	explanation on why minimisation actions were necessary (or why impacts could not be avoided first)		Yes (101-2)				
actions mitigation hierarchy relation	Explanation if restoration and rehabilitation action is implemented as organisational activities are ongoing/have been terminated		Yes (101-2)				
actions mitigation hierarchy relation	Explanation of how species and ecosystems targeted through restoration and rehabilitation actions, and how they support recovery)		Yes (101-2)				
actions mitigation hierarchy relation	% of restoration and rehabilitation action (to size affected)		Yes (V -101-2)				
restoration and rehabilitation actions	viability of restoration and rehabilitation action (without constraints that hinder successful implementation over time)		Yes (V -101-2)				
actions mitigation hierarchy relation	measurability of restoration and rehabilitation action (objectives defined and regularly monitored)		Yes (V -101-2)				
actions mitigation hierarchy relation	Biodiversity offsets were used in action plan		Yes (101-2, but see actions above)	Yes (semi-narrative)			

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Indicator	Metric	TNFD	GRI	ESRS	Taxonomy	SFDR	ISSB
actions mitigation hierarchy relation	types of offsets used (e.g., averted loss, restoration, one-off)		Yes (101-2)				
actions mitigation hierarchy relation	phases that offset projects are in (e.g., close to completion)		Yes (101-2)				
actions mitigation hierarchy relation	if offset has been finalised, description of delivered outcomes		Yes (V - 101-2)				
actions mitigation hierarchy relation	goals of offset action(s)		Yes (101-2)				
actions mitigation hierarchy relation	description of how no net loss or net gain goal is demonstrated and verified		Yes (101-2)				
actions mitigation hierarchy relation	geographic location of offset action(s)		Yes (101-2)				
actions mitigation hierarchy relation	whether and how national legislation or principles of good offset practices (e.g. BBOP, IUCN policy on biodiversity offsets, OECD principles) are met		Yes (101-2)				
actions mitigation hierarchy relation	whether and how offset is certified or verified by third party		Yes (101-2)				
actions mitigation hierarchy relation	whether the offset generates co-benefits (e.g., also carbon capture and/or social and cultural benefits)		Yes (101-2)				
actions mitigation hierarchy relation	residual negative impact of activities (based on BBOP calculation)		Yes (V - 101-2)				
actions mitigation hierarchy relation	whether and how the offset is certified or verified by a third party		Yes (101-2)				
transformative potential of	how steps are taken to transition towards circular economy		Yes (V - 101-2)				

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Indicator	Metric	TNFD	GRI	ESRS	Taxonomy	SFDR	ISSB
actions in mitigation hierarchy							
transformative potential of actions in mitigation hierarchy	which actions advance sustainable use of biodiversity and how		Yes (V - 101-2)				
actions overview	Biodiversity action plan is carried out only by undertaking (individual action) using its resources (biodiversity and ecosystems)			Yes (V - semi-narrative)			
actions overview	Key action plan is part of wider action plan (collective action), of which undertaking is member (biodiversity and ecosystems)		Yes (101-2)	Yes (V - semi-narrative)			
actions overview	Additional information about action/project, its sponsors and other participants (biodiversity and ecosystems)			Yes (V - semi-narrative)			
actions overview	Explanation of how synergies and trade-offs between actions to manage biodiversity and climate change impacts are enhanced and reduced.		Yes (101-2)				
actions contributions	contribution to impact drivers and possible mitigation actions following mitigation hierarchy and main path-dependencies and locked-in assets and resources that are associated with biodiversity and ecosystems change			Yes (V - narrative)			
actions overview	explanation of necessity to implement biodiversity mitigation measures		Yes (101-2, explanation why impacts could not be avoided)	Yes (semi-narrative)			
actions contributions	if activities on sea beyond national jurisdiction, describe if processes and actions to ensure access and fair benefit-sharing of marine genetic resources are implemented		Yes (V - 101-3)				
actions overview	how did engagement with indigenous peoples inform voluntary actions		Yes (V - 101-3)				
actions overview	description of own operations and how organisation is responding to material impacts in its related value chain		Yes similar (101-2, actions taken to manage impacts in value chain)	Yes (V - narrative)			
actions overview	description of actions taken to achieve equitable social outcomes		Yes (101-2)				

Table 10: Indicators and metrics for corporate policies and actions

(C) refers to core indicators of the TNFD, whereas (A) refers to additional indicators of the TNFD.

V refers to voluntary indicators of the GRI and the ESRS.

Lever of Change 2: Strategic Actions

Another critical part of the EU's biodiversity policy are so-called strategic actions. These actions complement strategic frameworks and legislations such that they constitute the actions through which the EU aims to reach the goals outlined in its Biodiversity Strategy. Overall, the EU has defined over 100 strategic actions in the Biodiversity Strategy Actions Tracker. Given that the EU's policies should enable rapid and holistic actions to achieve the EU's biodiversity goals, the strategic actions put forward as part of the Biodiversity Strategy can be regarded as second key lever of change.

The effectiveness of the strategic actions as levers of change can again be analyzed by how well they align with the EU's policy foci (biodiversity loss driver minimization, nature protection, nature restoration, governance, support activities, and financing). The subsequent sections thus review the foci areas of the actions and present how these map onto the previously identified EU's policy foci.

Key action areas of protecting and restoring nature

Since the strategic actions are concrete steps to reaching the EU's goals outlined in its Biodiversity Strategy, we analyzed how the actions and focus area map onto these goals. As such, the EU Biodiversity Strategy outlines four broad goals that need to be addressed to tackle biodiversity loss. On the one hand, it aims to establish 1) a coherent network of protected areas and 2) an EU Nature Restoration Plan. On the other hand, it aims to 3) enable transformative change and foster 4) external EU action and an ambitious global biodiversity agenda. Since the strategic actions represent the concrete steps to implement these four goals, we mapped the actions onto the biodiversity strategy's goals to understand where the EU's policy attention should be directed to.

Overall, the EU's biodiversity actions can be allocated to those four biodiversity goals as follows (see figure 9). 50% of the EU's actions currently contribute to the goal to establish the EU Nature Restoration Plan. 22% are intended to create transformative change, 19% aim to promote an ambitious global biodiversity agenda and approximately 9% aim to create a coherent network of protected areas. This suggests that the Nature Restoration Plan is by far the most critical aspect to reach the biodiversity goals. It is therefore critical for the EU to develop and adopt policies that facilitate the plan's implementation.

Figure 9: Strategic actions by EU biodiversity strategy goals

Triple goal of biodiversity loss driver minimization, governance, and nature protection

Building on the above, we also looked at how the actions and four EU biodiversity strategy goals relate to the five policy focus areas (driver minimization, provision of more adequate financing, governance, nature protection, nature restoration, and support). As such, we found similar focus areas in the strategic actions as in the policy (see earlier section). In fact, figure 10 shows that the EU's actions have the same focus areas as its policies. However, while the policies focus primarily on biodiversity loss driver minimization (see earlier sections and figure 5), the actions put a triple emphasis on driver minimization (21%), nature protection (21%), and governance (21%). A further 15% of the actions are intended to add to promote support activities, and 14% of the actions outlined by the EU are aimed at providing more adequate biodiversity financing. The EU's actions, therefore, do not match the policy focus such that the prior put (relatively) less emphasis on biodiversity loss driver minimization but relatively more emphasis on nature protection and the development of biodiversity governance.

Figure 10: Focus areas in biodiversity actions

Looking in more detail at how the EU's actions map on to the five major biodiversity loss drivers identified by the IPBES (2019), our analysis reveals that the EU focuses primarily on the reduction of pollution (45% of actions can be allocated to it). Figure 11 below also demonstrates that the EU's actions focus on addressing the drivers land- and sea-use change (23%) and the exploitation of organisms (23%). Climate change and the control of invasive species are, like in the policies, only a minor focus of the EU actions (ca. 5% of all actions can be allocated to the drivers respectively).

Figure 11: Biodiversity loss driver action focus

The above analysis suggests that the EU’s actions are broadly in line with its overall policy focus. The biodiversity loss driver of pollution is regarded as most important in both policies and actions. However, while EU policies only regard the direct exploitation of organisms as an important second biodiversity loss driver, EU actions regard the direct exploitation of organisms as well as land- and sea-use change as critical secondary drivers. The actions also put less emphasis on addressing the drivers of climate change and invasive alien species than the policies.

Figure 12 furthermore shows that the EU’s policy foci are supporting actions in all four biodiversity goals. Notably, it suggests that the policy focus on biodiversity loss driver minimization already supports the EU’s goal to implement the Nature Restoration Plan (see red bar in first column in figure 12 below). Yet, the actions for the implementation of the Nature Restoration Plan also require policy in nature protection (13%), nature restoration (8%), and the development of supporting structures (e.g., education) (6%). Given the overall policy focus of biodiversity loss driver minimization (figure 5), the above results suggest that the EU is broadly fostering the implementation of the EU Nature Restoration Plan. However, the limited policy focus nature restoration may complicate this implementation. Further, since there is limited policy focus on the areas containing actions that are relevant for transformative change (see yellow columns in figure 11 below), it is questionable whether EU policies do enough to reduce biodiversity loss more generally.

Figure 12: How policy focus areas support biodiversity strategy goals

Biodiversity Finance Landscape

Biodiversity finance is broadly defined as “practice of raising and managing capital and using financial and economic mechanisms to support sustainable biodiversity management. It is about leveraging and effectively managing economic incentives, policies, and capital to achieve the long-term well-being of nature and our society” (UNDP BIOFIN, 2018). As such biodiversity finance is concerned with the conservation – which comprises both protection and restoration – or rewilding of nature (Seidl et al., 2020). Biodiversity finance is an emerging practice, which is why there are few instruments that explicitly focus on the EU’s main policy foci of biodiversity loss driver minimization, nature protection, and restoration (e.g., Binnie et al., 2022; Nedopil, 2022; Seidl et al., 2020). However, recent studies show that investors increasingly care about biodiversity (e.g., Garel et al., 2024; Klug et al., 2023; Wagstaff et al., 2024) and new biodiversity finance mechanisms are developing globally (e.g., Binnie et al., 2022; Flammer et al., 2023; OECD, 2020). The rest of this report reviews and discusses current biodiversity finance mechanisms.

Biodiversity finance mechanisms

There are many different biodiversity finance mechanisms available (see e.g., Flammer et al., 2023; Harrer et al., 2023). These mechanisms can be split into revenue-raising and financing instruments. Figure 13 provides an overview of those currently available. **Revenue-raising instruments** focus on charging corporations or nations for their adverse impact on biodiversity. These instruments excel in increasing sovereign conservation budgets (Dempsey et al., 2022; Schuster et al., 2018) and as such are particularly relevant for national and supra-national institutions (e.g., national governments or supra-national bodies such as the EU) (BIOFIN, 2021). **Biodiversity financing instruments** focus on providing capital to corporations and projects that work to conserve nature (Harrer et al., 2023). Since biodiversity financing instruments focus on delivering (measurable) returns, they can also be effective in scaling nature conservation practices (Dempsey et al., 2022). Thus, given the need to support and scale practices for nature conservation (IPBES, 2019; IPCC, 2023), financing instruments are often regarded particularly important to tackle biodiversity loss (OECD, 2019, 2020; zu Ermgassen & Löfqvist, 2024).

Figure 13: Biodiversity finance instruments based on Harrer et al. (2023, p. 361) adapted from OECD (2019, 2020)

Revenue-raising biodiversity finance instruments

The literature describes two primary revenue-raising instruments (see again figure 13): 1) a biodiversity tax and 2) biodiversity fees and charges (e.g., Dempsey et al., 2022). Similar to a CO₂ tax, a **biodiversity tax** is an unrequited payment to general governments based on the amount of biodiversity destruction (i.e., the payer is charged for destruction and gets nothing in return). The rationale behind such taxes is to penalize those who destroy/pollute. The OECD suggests that in 2021 62 countries had 234 biodiversity-relevant taxes in place (OECD, 2021). Most of these taxes are on national and sub-national level (e.g., state or county). With 25 taxes, the US has most biodiversity taxes in place, closely followed by Spain (ca. 16) and Denmark (ca. 14). Brazil, Indonesia, Kenya, Namibia, Panama are among the OECD developing countries with the fewest biodiversity taxes.

In comparison to biodiversity taxes, **biodiversity fees and charges** refer to requited payments to governments based on how much is consumed/used. That is, the payer is charged depending on how much (e.g., ecosystem services, natural capital etc.) they use. Biodiversity fees and charges include, for instance, charges for groundwater abstraction, charges for land-based sewage discharges, fees on hunting licenses, entrances fees for national parks, and non-compliance fines. Here, the OECD suggests that in 2021 44 countries had 157 biodiversity-relevant fees and charges. With 16 fees and charges Canada leads the list, closely followed by Croatia (14), Spain (13), and Germany (12). Botswana, Chile, and the Congo are among the OECD countries with the least biodiversity fees and charges (OECD, 2021).

Biodiversity financing instruments

There are numerous biodiversity financing instruments (see figure 13). Biodiversity financing instrument can be differentiated depending on who provides the capital. As such there can be **public**, **private**, and **hybrid** biodiversity financing instruments. Figure 14 provides a simplified overview of capital providers and how they may use biodiversity financing to serve different purposes. The subsequent sections discuss biodiversity financing instruments with regard to their issuers. We also discuss the (still) emerging evidence of the instruments' effectiveness.

Figure 14: Simplified overview of issuers of biodiversity financing instruments (based on Ermgassen and Löfqvist (2024, p. R415) who adapted from Löfqvist et al. (2023)).

Public biodiversity financing instruments

Harrer et al. (2023) show that the public sector often issues biodiversity financing in the form of **direct government expenditures** (e.g., nature restoration funds), **environmental subsidies**, **development finance**, and **debt-for-nature swaps**. Restoration funds are particularly popular, such that governments and development banks increasingly provide “lump sums”, which organizations can access to fund conservation or rewilding activities, for example, to conserve native plants and species (OECD, 2021). Debt-for-nature swaps are also found to be increasingly common (e.g., Nedopil et al., 2024). These swaps refer to a government’s cancellation of debt based on the debtor’s commitment to supporting biodiversity projects in the local country (and currency) (Burand, 1989; Hansen, 1989; OECD, 2007; Zimmerman, 1991). Since governments of developing countries often cannot mount the interest burden of debt, debt-for-nature swaps enable them to channel international capital and contribute to the sustainable development of their own countries. An example is the 2015 \$21.6 million debt release of the Seychelles to develop a marine spatial plan, or the 2023 \$300 million debt-for-climate swap of Barbados to upgrade its water infrastructure. Also in 2023, Ecuador administered the biggest debt-for-nature swap to date. The government committed to spending \$18 million annually for 20 years and to invest this money in conservation project in the Galapagos Islands. While debt-for-nature swaps may free up large amounts of capital for conservation in developing countries, they require significant size to have an impact, that is, if the area addressed is not large enough, then they most likely are not effective. Most swaps to date do not meet this size requirement (Nedopil et al., 2024; Whiting, 2023).

Private biodiversity financing instruments

Private sector biodiversity financing is delivered primarily through (voluntary) biodiversity credits or offsets, impact investing, or philanthropy. While **philanthropy** refers to the benevolent giving (donations) based on purpose (e.g., as many foundations do, the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation being one of the most influential ones), **impact investing** combines purpose with financial return.

Just like philanthropists, impact investors are characterized by their intentional focus on investments for purpose (Agrawal & Hockerts, 2019). However, impact investors also require a viable and scalable business model (Bugg-Levine & Goldstein, 2009; Höchstädter & Scheck, 2014). Impact investing is often conducted by small impact funds, who directly invest via equities or loans (e.g., Big Issue Invest in the UK) (Newmark & Pena, 2023). Given this direct nature of the investment, impact investors interact more actively with their investees and are able to provide more patient capital. This in turn makes impact investing more effective than philanthropy (Roundy et al., 2017); also for biodiversity outcomes (Thompson, 2023). An example of an impact investor who focuses on biodiversity outcomes is Fair Capital in Switzerland. Although impact investing has clear impact intentions, it often is unable to deliver on long-term impact, thereby also jeopardizing financial returns (e.g., Schätzlein et al., 2020; Schlütter et al., 2023). Consequently, it remains difficult to scale impact investments, which further hampers their impact potential.

Biodiversity offsets, just like CO₂ offsets, enable companies to voluntarily compensate for irreversible biodiversity impacts (Alvarado-Quesada et al., 2014; Koh et al., 2019). By investing in conservation projects elsewhere, companies can balance out lasting negative effects of development efforts in their own sites (Barnes et al., 2023; Bull et al., 2013; Buschke et al., 2019; Grimm & Köppel, 2019; Villarroya et al., 2014). So-called “no net loss”, or “net-positive” projects often classify as biodiversity offset projects (Bull et al., 2013; Cuckston, 2013). Although impact investing is often considered the more effective private sector financing instrument for biodiversity outcomes (as it provides direct and more patient capital to support e.g., underrepresented communities) biodiversity offsets offer quicker rewards and as such they are more common (zu Ermgassen & Löfqvist, 2024). This is because “impact” in impact investing is holistic and highly context-sensitive (Schlütter et al., 2023), but the value of nature is simplistic and relatively context-agnostic in biodiversity offsets (i.e., a pre-defined value of biodiversity lost in a development area must be compensated for in an offset area on a “like-for-like”-basis) (Kay, 2015). Biodiversity offsets have also been criticized to rarely follow the mitigation hierarchy (avoid, mitigate, and only then offset) (e.g., IUCN, 2016) and through this offer companies a rather “cheap way out” of biodiversity conservation (Cares et al., 2023; Gutierrez et al., 2021). Due to their “like-for-like” logic, they have also been criticized for the exclusion of local communities’ knowledge and values (Tupala et al., 2022), for inequitable decisions on what areas should be protected and destroyed (Griffiths et al., 2019), for failures to inspire pro-environmental behavior (Cinner et al., 2021; Sonter et al., 2020), displacements of values (e.g., offset areas are far away from impact areas and as such the global south may experience more immediate effects than the global north) (Schuster et al., 2018; Tupala et al., 2022; zu Ermgassen et al., 2019), or for the over-emphasis of biodiversity-loss ex ante to increase the effect later on (Tregidga, 2013; zu Ermgassen et al., 2019).

Such criticism notwithstanding, biodiversity offsets are highly popular and increasingly also included in biodiversity policies (e.g., Rampling et al., 2024). Governments often aim to incentivize companies to deliver so-called “net-positive” biodiversity gains. To do so, governments in collaboration with landowners generate so-called **biodiversity credits** which they then sell to companies on the market. A biodiversity credit is a pre-defined unit of value that captures the effect of conservation projects. An example is the value of the amount of restored land. One of the most prominent examples of a biodiversity credit policy is the UK’s Biodiversity Net Gain (BNG) scheme¹. The scheme asks landowners to invest in biodiversity credits if they are not able to generate enough direct (i.e., on-site) positive net gain². Although biodiversity offsets and biodiversity credits are both market-based mechanisms that allow companies to compensate for damage, there is a difference. Biodiversity offsets focus primarily on offsetting adverse impacts stemming from development projects (“no net loss”). In contrast, biodiversity credits aim to promote positive biodiversity gains (“net gain”).

¹ See also the official explanation of the BNG scheme: <https://www.gov.uk/guidance/understanding-biodiversity-net-gain>.

² Positive net gain is calculated through a biodiversity metric based on standardized biodiversity units. For more information see here: <https://www.gov.uk/guidance/biodiversity-metric-calculate-the-biodiversity-net-gain-of-a-project-or-development#:~:text=For%20BNG%20%2C%20biodiversity%20is%20measured,contains%20before%20development%20takes%20place.>

Hybrid biodiversity financing instruments

Besides the above “pure” public and private options, there are also hybrid biodiversity financing options (e.g., Harrer et al., 2023). Hybrid financing options are issued through a collaboration of public and private organizations. Public investors, such as development banks (e.g., the World Bank), often absorb initial losses and push down the investment risk. This enables private investors to get involved in what otherwise be an unattractive project. The collaboration of public and private investors makes hybrid biodiversity financing options more scalable than other financing options such as impact investing (Christiansen, 2021; Robinson-Tillett, 2024; Rode et al., 2019).

Currently there are two main mechanisms of hybrid biodiversity financing available. The first mechanism focuses on rewarding often unrecognized work and includes financing instruments such as **Payments for Environmental Services (PES)**. The second mechanism focuses on providing capital at scale and includes financing instruments such as bonds and equities. PES reward local project owners, communities, and organizations for the maintenance of nature’s ecosystem services. According to the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (2005) there are four major ecosystem services that the rewards can be provided for: 1) provisioning (e.g., timber, water, or food), 2) regulatory, including pollution and flood control, 3) supporting (photosynthesis, or nutrient cycling), and 4) cultural (spiritual, recreational, or aesthetic) services. Since the work to maintain such ecosystem services often remains hidden, PES intend to recognize the value of such ecosystem services (Constanza, 1997) and enable beneficiaries to compensate those who maintain those services. Often the compensation takes place via an issuance of biodiversity or carbon credits. Through this PES intend not only to allocate more money to local projects, but also to motivate local project owners to adopt more nature-positive practices, which in turn helps to secure the flow of ecosystem services in the long-term. PES are funded voluntarily and both private and public beneficiaries can allocate capital through them (Wunder et al., 2020).

Many of the currently available PES are funded through the so-called REDD+ framework³. “REDD” stands for Reducing Emissions from Deforestation and forest Degradation in developing countries, and the “+” refers to additional forest-related activities that protect the climate through carbon capture (‘services’). The REDD+ framework enables developing countries to receive payment if they reduce deforestation and, through it, emissions. The most famous PES under the REDD+ framework is the Rimba Raya Conservation (RRC) project⁴. It is set in the Rimba Raya biodiversity reserve in Indonesia and is one of the largest REDD+ peat swamp forest projects in the world. The agreed PES seeks to reward the landowners in the Rimba Raya reserve for their carbon offset efforts. To do so, the RRC generates carbon credits from high conservation value peat swamp forest. Among many assurers, the Verified Carbon Standard (VCS) is one of the most critical ones for the RRC project. VCS defines and assures the criteria by which the value of the carbon credits is assessed. The REDD+ framework and the RRC project are, however, not the only examples for PES. Under the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), the EU has also been supporting sustainable forestry since 2000.

However, only in 2018 did the EU issue a dedicated PES pilot program⁵. This program included two areas in Portugal: the protected landscape of the Serra do Acor (Area de Paisagem Protegida da Serra do Acor) and the Tagus International Natural Park (Parque Natural do Tejo Interacional). In both locations the program aimed to reward local forest management entities, forest producers’ organizations, wasteland management entities, and other natural or legal persons for the maintenance and promotion of mixed forest stands (e.g., oak and chestnut), rehabilitation of agricultural areas, water stream management, and the denaturalization of forest areas with native species (e.g., cork oak), among others. PES are often regarded as a highly effective biodiversity financing instruments because they make previously unrecognized value visible and redistribute power to underrepresented communities (Wunder et al., 2020). PES are, however, also criticized because they grant landowners relatively high power, and seem to favor distinct activities such as rewilding over others (e.g., the active management and nature-positive agricultural use) (Kay, 2015). In addition, to date PES are mostly funded by governments (e.g., to fund Natura 2000 regions) who

³ For more information see also <https://unfccc.int/topics/land-use/workstreams/redd/what-is-redd>

⁴ For more information see also <https://rimba-raya.com/>

⁵ For more information see also <https://environment.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2021-10/Payments%20for%20ecosystem%20services.pdf>

then also carry the burden of the risk of mismanagement (Abildtrup et al., 2021; Bárbara et al., 2024; Bell et al., 2018; Davies et al., 2016; Kangas & Ollikainen, 2022; Kay, 2015; Okiria et al., 2021).

The second mechanism of hybrid biodiversity financing includes instruments such as **bonds and equities**. In the case of biodiversity equities, a private investor (e.g., an asset manager or a bank) usually bundles capital into a thematic fund and, through the collaboration with NGOs and other local specialists, invests capital directly into organizations. Since equities are a common financing instrument of large corporations, biodiversity equities are often said to be able to bring large organizations on board of the biodiversity agenda (Flammer et al., 2023). The asset manager Robeco, for instance, recognized this opportunity and was one of the first to launch dedicated Biodiversity equity funds in 2022. Together with WWF Netherlands, Robeco arranged four thematic investment clusters around sustainable land and sea use activities⁶, specifically 1) Sustainable land use, focused on forests and woodlands, cultivated lands and urban environments; 2) Freshwater Networks, including pollution prevention, purification and treatment and habitat protection; 3) Marine Systems, covering fisheries aquaculture and ocean conservation; and 4) Traceable Products, such as foods, fibers and raw materials.

Biodiversity bonds refer to publicly (i.e., from sovereigns) or privately (i.e., from organizations) issued debt on the primary market, often subsequently traded on the secondary market among large institutional investors such as pension fund or endowments and insurance companies. Bonds are hybrid when they involve rating agencies and development banks as guarantors (Baker et al., 2022; Flammer, 2021; Tang & Zhang, 2020) who make rather risky investments attractive (Kölbel & Lambillon, 2022). Since bonds are issued on the secondary market, they grant their issuers access a larger capital pool (*vis-à-vis* for example regular loans) without granting too much power to the investor (Flammer, 2021). With regard to biodiversity, the issuance of bonds can enable large institutional investors (notably asset managers) to allocate at least parts of their portfolios to conservation imperatives (Maltais & Nykvist; Tang & Zhang, 2020).

As such, there are various types of “biodiversity bonds”. The most important ones are green, blue, sustainability, and sustainability-linked bonds. These types of bonds differ not only in their name, but most importantly in how they allocate capital to biodiversity outcomes. Green bonds, for instance, are characterized by the issuers’ commitment to use the proceeds specifically for a green purpose. A cooperative that issues a green bond, for example, may commit to using the capital only for funding rewilding activities. Examples of green bonds include those of the Philippine BDO Unibank, Common land, Rabobank in the Netherlands, Stora Enso, or the Indonesia’s Barito Pacific and Michelin bond for sustainable rubber. Given this commitment, green bonds are often seen as an important financing option to channel large-scale international capital to nature-positive or conservation projects (Flammer, 2021; Friede et al., 2015). So-called blue and sustainability bonds follow the same principles as green bonds (Jones et al., 2020; Lebellet et al., 2020; McFarland, 2018). Issuers of blue bonds commit to using the proceeds for “blue” projects – which are always water-related (hence: blue) – only (Thompson, 2022). Issuers of sustainability bonds commit to investing in a combination of social and green projects, and for the latter two bonds, the issuers also commit to completing projects that follow state-licensed guidelines. The DC Water bond for storm-water runoff infrastructure is an example for a blue bond and the EIB sustainability awareness bond is an example for a sustainability bond. While the above biodiversity bond types are characterized by a distinct use of proceeds, sustainability-linked bonds differ. Sustainability-linked biodiversity bonds allow the proceeds to be used for various (also standard corporate) activities as long as they enable the organization or project to meet certain pre-set sustainability goals throughout the duration of the bond. A cooperative may, for example, use the proceeds of its sustainability-linked bond to fund harvesting equipment as long as this equipment helps the cooperative deliver on the pre-set sustainability goals.

Although some works show that hybrid green, blue and sustainability bonds can deliver on conservation goals (Bhutta et al., 2022; Dong et al., 2023; Fatica & Panzica, 2021; Flammer, 2021; March et al., 2024), Pichlmayer and Lehner (2024) suggest that sustainability-linked bonds demonstrate higher potential to effectively reach biodiversity outcomes. That is because the latter bonds are more

⁶ For more information see also <https://www.esgtoday.com/robeco-announces-launch-of-biodiversity-equities-strategy/>

flexible in the use of proceeds and therefore have the potential to enable more holistic adaptations and long-term transformative change.

The state of biodiversity finance

Although it is difficult to comprehensively analyze the state of biodiversity finance (as there is very little or incomplete data), the literature suggests that currently biodiversity finance is delivered primarily through revenue-raising (i.e., biodiversity fees and schemes) and public financing instruments (i.e., though subsidies or debt for nature swaps) (Löfqvist et al., 2023; zu Ermgassen & Löfqvist, 2024). zu Ermgassen and Löfqvist (2024), for instance, point to estimates which suggest that more than 80% of conservation finance is supplied by public financiers. The literature also suggests that the interest of the private sector to invest in nature conservation has increased (e.g., Binnie et al., 2022; Flammer et al., 2023; zu Ermgassen & Löfqvist, 2024). However, this interest is largely limited to voluntary credit markets (i.e., offsetting schemes) (zu Ermgassen & Löfqvist, 2024) and green bonds (Baker et al., 2022; Flammer, 2021). Given the potentially limited effectiveness of these financing instruments (as discussed in earlier sections), there is a need to critically review the role of the private sector in financing conservation outcomes.

Table 11 summarizes the most used biodiversity finance instruments based on insights from the literature. There is a focus on revenue-raising (tax) and public biodiversity financing instruments. If the private sector is involved, it is reliant on voluntary credit markets or on green/blue bonds.

Instrument	Primary funding source	Description	Example(s)
Sovereign sustainability linked bonds	Hybrid	Linking biodiversity gains to cost of government sovereign debt	Kenya's sustainability linked bond, Uruguay's ESG-linked bond, Chile's US\$ billion sustainability linked bond, France's biodiversity conservation bond
Debt-for nature swaps	Public	Write-off of debt to preserve natural environment	Ecuador in an attempt to write off debt by committing to protect Galapagos islands
Corporate blue/green bonds	Hybrid	Linking nature/marine pollution reduction and protection to funding	Philippine BDO Unibank, Common land, Rabobank in the Netherlands, Stora Enso Green Bond, Indonesia's Barito Pacific and Michelin bond for sustainable rubber, DC Water bond for storm-water run-off infrastructure, EIB sustainability awareness bonds
Biodiversity credit (markets)	Public	To promote establishment of projects that protect or restore ecosystems	Colombia and New Zealand
Biodiversity tax	Public	Tax income solely allocated to bolstering nature	Fiji's Environment and Climate Adaption Levy

Instrument	Primary funding source	Description	Example(s)
Landscape funds	Public	Mobilize funding for communities and the conservation and adaption of landscapes to protect and restore biodiversity.	Asia Climate-Smart Landscape Fund in Indonesia, OECD or UK Biodiverse Landscape Fund, Legacy landscapes Fund in Germany, Brazil's Amazon Fund

Table 11: Most common biodiversity funding instruments to date (see also Harrer et al., 2023)

According to MSCI (2024), all types of the previously mentioned “biodiversity” bonds (green, blue, sustainability, sustainability-linked) have been on the rise in the last five years. Yet, this rise can be attributed notably to sovereigns increasingly using these bonds to fund biodiversity projects (Mastouri et al., 2023). Sustainability-linked bonds, and in particular privately issued sustainability-linked bonds, currently only represent a small fraction of the global bond market (Herbling, 2024; MSCI, 2024). According to Bloomberg, the number of newly issued green and sustainability-linked biodiversity bonds has increased steadily since 2015 (see figures 15 and 16).

Figure 15: Number of green bonds 2015-2024 issued globally (source: Bloomberg)

Figure 16: Number of sustainability-linked biodiversity bonds 2015-2024 issued globally (source: Bloomberg)

Figure 17 and 18 also reveal that a large proportion of biodiversity bonds – particularly sustainability-linked bonds (see figure 17) – are issued by governments. The high number of issued biodiversity bonds from supranational (SNAT) governments suggests that these instruments are commonly issued by multiple governments together. For more information see Appendix 3a.

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Figure 17: Green bond issue volume per top 25 region and year (source: Bloomberg)

Figure 18: Sustainability linked biodiversity bond issue volume per top 25 region and year (source: Bloomberg)

The Principles of Responsible Investment's (PRI) signatory data confirms the trend towards publicly issued biodiversity financing instruments and a focus on green bonds (for more information see Appendix 3b). Table 12 below demonstrates that private investors are increasingly aware of the need to protect biodiversity. Since the publication of the Paris Agreement in 2015, the percentage of signatories mentioning biodiversity (BD) as an issue in their investment strategies has slowly but steadily increased over the last six years. Overall, relative to the overall PRI signatory base, biodiversity aware investors represent only a fraction of the sustainable finance market (11% in 2020).

Year	Total Signatories	Average AUM	BD Signatories	% BD Signatories	% BD IM	% BD AO
2016	1030	\$ 539,208,143,726,952.00	31	3 %	48 %	52 %
2017	1187	\$ 539,400,501,796,632.00	86	7 %	73 %	27 %
2018	1365	\$ 538,416,496,331,753.00	118	9 %	76 %	24 %
2019	1704	\$ 539,026,603,779,147.00	207	12 %	83 %	17 %
2020	2099	\$ 538,824,983,415,882.00	238	11 %	82 %	18 %

Table 12: Relevance of biodiversity in investment strategies of PRI investors

AUM = assets under management, BD = biodiversity, IM = investment managers, AO = asset owners

Most of PRI's biodiversity investors are located in Europe. Over 60% of the global investors are registered in Europe, with most of them in the UK, France, the Netherlands, Switzerland, and Germany. Investors from Oceania, Asia (notably from Indonesia and Singapore), and Africa (notably South Africa, Namibia, and the United Arab Emirates) remained a stable minority, while the share of biodiversity investors from the Americas (notably the United States, Canada, and Brazil) increased slightly from an initial 3% to 18% in 2020. Figure 19 summarizes these observations.

Figure 19: Headquarters of PRI biodiversity investors by region

Figure 20 further shows the asset classes in which PRI investors incorporate biodiversity.

Figure 20: Asset classes in which PRI investors state that they incorporate biodiversity

LE = Listed Equity, FI = Fixed Income, PE = Private Equity, RE = Real Estate, INF = Infrastructure

NB: PRI also notes Hedge Funds as a major asset class. However, given that PRI signatories did not mention biodiversity in hedge funds, they are not shown in this summary.

Although PRI biodiversity investors increasingly consider biodiversity in their investments (see above), only a fraction mention biodiversity as a strategic focus area through which they, for example, engage in the development of the biodiversity finance market. As such, the number of PRI signatories stating that they put a strategic focus on biodiversity has risen from 9% in 2016 to ca. 25% in 2019 and 2020 (see figure 21). However, the relative number remains small (i.e., the number refers to 25% of ca. 10% of all PRI signatories).

Figure 21: PRI biodiversity signatories with a dedicated strategic focus on biodiversity

Overall, a critical reason for the lack of the involvement of the private sector may be that nature is not yet regarded as an asset class (Rivett-Carnac, 2023). Yet, another perhaps more far-reaching reason may be that conservation does – after many years of effort (see e.g., Bishop, 2013) – still not present an investment case. At the Sustainable Fitch-organized “What’s next for biodiversity: Unpacking Financing options and trends” webinar, Irina Likhachova (2023) stated that “it [conservation] is simply not what companies do”. Thus, while pollution, waste, restoration of land regenerative and organic agriculture are increasingly presented as viable investment cases (for example in the impact investing sphere. TcforBE’s Work Package 5 on corporate and regenerative nature-based enterprises will also look at examples of these investment cases), for biodiversity to become a more attractive investment case, it requires a new outcomes-based funding models that leverage well established financing principles with best practices (Rivett-Carnac, 2023). Based on the above review of the biodiversity financing instruments, sustainability-linked bonds may present a particularly suitable outcomes-based funding model that allows to deliver the required financing on scale.

Policy and finance mechanisms for positive biodiversity objectives

The main purpose of this report was to provide an overview of biodiversity policies and available biodiversity finance options from the EU. The study shows that globally and in the EU there are numerous policy foci promoting finance as a lever and many biodiversity finance mechanisms in use. There is a largely consistent biodiversity policy of the EU; with minor mismatches, for instance, regarding the strategic actions and the focus of biodiversity indicators and metrics.

However, as noted in the introduction, another purpose of this report was to critically evaluate EU biodiversity policies and biodiversity finance options regarding their ability to contribute to global biodiversity objectives. To this end, the IPBES’ (2019) Global Assessment Report represents the most comprehensive scientific evidence on the state of biodiversity globally. Recalling figure 1, the IPBES report outlines five major drivers of biodiversity loss (pollution, direct exploitation of organisms, land- and sea-use change, climate change, and invasive alien species) and argues that for biodiversity objectives to be reached, these drivers need to be addressed according to their relevance.

Figure 22: Recalling figure 1: Biodiversity loss driver impact per realm (IPBES, 2019)

Reading the IPBES report’s findings in the light of this scientific evidence, the following sections briefly outline some key limitations and opportunities of the EU biodiversity policy and biodiversity finance in the light of global biodiversity agendas.

Limitations and opportunities of EU policy promoted levers

Although the EU has a strong policy focus on biodiversity restoration and protection, its policy is currently limited by three interrelated types of means-ends decoupling:

1. The EU's policy does not align with scientific evidence:

The EU's policy focus is on biodiversity loss driver minimization (see figure 6), in particular the reduction of pollution and direct exploitation of organisms (see figure 7). This focus is relevant. However:

- scientific evidence (notably the IPBES, 2019 Global Assessment Report) suggests that sea- and land-use change is the biggest biodiversity loss driver (see figure 1).
- the EU's strategic actions follow scientific evidence and therefore lack legislative backing.

Overall, the misalignment of EU policy – and current political guidance - with scientific evidence not only endangers the successful minimization of biodiversity loss drivers. It also puts at risk the effectiveness of the implementation of EU's Nature Restoration Plan and transformative change agenda, both of which are the key focus of the strategic actions within Europe. The upcoming CSDDD might provide a better focus on telecoupled value chain activities, yet it is not without its own political controversy.

2. The Directorate Generals sponsoring the various EU policy documents do not match the block's goal of creating a unified biodiversity market:

The EU's policy has a long history of being developed by the Directorate Generals (DGs) with the highest subject expertise (see table 3). Such subject expertise is undoubtedly important when it comes to biodiversity. However:

- while most strategic actions are co-developed by many DGs, the majority of EU policies are developed independently by subject experts (notably the DG Environment) (see table 3 again).
- system and market experts (e.g., DG FISMA) are less involved in the EU's policy development (see table 3).

Overall, the one-sided reliance on the subject experts of DG Environment to develop the EU's biodiversity policy not only poses the risk of a lack of acceptance of other subject matter experts (or non-expert stakeholders for that matter). It also largely excludes system-level and market experts which puts at risk the EU's goal to create a unified biodiversity market.

3. The EU's biodiversity indicators and metrics are misaligned with science and primarily anthropocentric:

The EU's biodiversity reporting framework (notably under the EU Taxonomy, the CSRD, and the SFDR) is comprehensive and globally among the most developed ones. However:

- The reporting framework builds primarily on the (natural) capital and ecosystem biodiversity accounting approach and as such it largely follows an anthropocentric accounting logic (see tables 6 and 7).
- The indicators and metrics put forward in this framework emphasize the biodiversity loss drivers of pollution and climate change (see around table 8), and therefore also do not follow the scientific evidence (notably the IPBES, 2019 Global Assessment Report) which suggests that sea- and land-use change is the biggest biodiversity loss driver (see figure 1 and 22).
- The indicators and metrics primarily relate to (economic) impacts/dependencies and as such prioritize the instrumental (economic use) value of nature (see around table 9).

- Although the EU's biodiversity reporting framework puts good governance at its core (see table 10) it almost entirely neglects indigenous peoples and relational values of nature.

Overall, the anthropocentric and instrumental (economic use) focus of the EU's biodiversity reporting framework not only risks underestimating the value of nature itself, but also renders the EU unable to deliver on the Global Biodiversity Framework agenda which seeks to re-inspire place-based nature stewardship.

Despite all the limitations there are also some great opportunities and levers on the horizon:

4. EU policies eurocentric focus, until recently:

Much of the EU policy focuses on the impacts on biodiversity on EU member states' national territory. An example is the Nature Restoration regulation which focuses exclusively on Europe. However increasingly the EU has been increasingly enacting regulations and policies that are unilateral and extra-jurisdictional, having impacts on biodiversity with trading partners in producer countries, such as the EU Timber Regulation (EUTR), EU Deforestation Regulation (EUDR), Directive on Corporate Sustainability Reporting (CSRD) and EU Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive (CSDDD).

5. Comprehensive and developed reporting framework:

- The EU's biodiversity reporting frameworks (e.g., under the CSRD, SFDR, and EU Taxonomy) are globally among the most advanced.
- Indicators and metrics are in place to enhance corporate accountability, including innovative financial disclosures.

6. Focus on financial instruments:

- The EU actively develops biodiversity financing mechanisms, such as green bonds and biodiversity-linked bonds, which can mobilize resources for conservation and restoration efforts.
- These tools encourage private sector involvement and incentivize biodiversity-positive investments.

7. Strategic actions and normative frameworks:

- The shift from coercion (regulations) to normativity (strategic frameworks) in recent years allows for broader stakeholder engagement.
- Frameworks like the European Green Deal and the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 outline a cohesive vision for long-term sustainability.

8. Expanding the scope beyond Europe:

- Increasing focus on extra-jurisdictional impacts through policies like the EU Deforestation Regulation and Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive.
- These policies address biodiversity impacts in trading partner countries and promote global conservation.

9. Integration of biodiversity into financial decision-making:

- Efforts to link biodiversity conservation with financial stability and performance encourage systemic changes in corporate and financial sectors.
- This approach enhances transparency and fosters responsible environmental stewardship.

10. Alignment with global frameworks:

- The EU policies complement international initiatives such as the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework, focusing on global conservation targets like protecting 30% of land and marine areas by 2030.

Limitations and opportunities of biodiversity finance mechanisms

Our analysis shows that the global biodiversity finance sector and mechanisms are developing rapidly. Yet, they are limited by two critical issues:

1. Finance objectives are at odds with scientific evidence:

Scientific evidence points to the importance of prioritizing conservation targets (see e.g., the IPBES (2019)). However:

- Conservation objectives are at odds with business objectives and therefore only pollution, waste, land restoration and a few other initiatives are currently perceived as viable investment cases (see e.g., Likhachova, 2023).
- the preference for financing mechanisms that target “net-positive” or “no net loss” objectives – notably biodiversity offsets/credits (see notably table 11) – likely obscures conservation needs.

Overall, the predominant focus on finance mechanisms that focus on “netting” (such as biodiversity offsets/credits), not only puts the EU at risk of failing to deliver on its biodiversity goals and the 30x30 target of the Global Biodiversity Framework. It also demonstrates that there is an urgent need for more outcome-focused biodiversity financing instruments (such as sustainability-linked bonds).

2. Financing biodiversity outcomes is not yet effective and primarily shouldered by the public sector:

The biodiversity finance landscape is broad, covering revenue raising finance as well as public and private financing instruments (see figure 13). However:

- currently there is a focus on revenue-raising biodiversity finance instruments such as biodiversity taxes (OECD, 2019, 2020).
- there also is a focus on (less scalable) public biodiversity financing instruments such as debt-for nature-swaps (see table 11, and figures 17 and 18).
- regarding more scalable financing mechanisms, there is a focus on biodiversity offsets/credits as well as green (and blue) bonds (see table 11 and figures 15, 16, and 20), which have been shown to cause problems.
- sustainability-linked bonds, which may be able to deliver the required outcome-focused capital to address biodiversity loss on scale, are currently underrepresented in the market (see notably figure 16).

Overall, the focus on public biodiversity finance not only risks being unable to deliver biodiversity funding at the necessary scale. It also points to limited accountability assumptions that underly the current private biodiversity financing instruments.

Despite all the limitations there are also some opportunities and levers to be found:

3. Emerging sustainability-linked financing mechanisms:

- Sustainability-linked bonds offer an innovative avenue to scale financing for biodiversity outcomes. These instruments align financial returns with measurable biodiversity targets, creating outcome-focused investment opportunities.
- Increasing adoption of such instruments can drive transformative changes in biodiversity conservation financing.

4. Integration of conservation objectives into investment cases:

- Despite current challenges, there is growing potential for aligning conservation goals with viable investment opportunities.
- Financial instruments emphasizing measurable outcomes, such as conservation impact metrics, can attract private sector participation while supporting biodiversity goals.

5. Broadening the scope of private sector engagement:

- Enhanced private sector accountability in biodiversity finance can diversify funding sources.
- Mechanisms like biodiversity credits, when designed with strong outcome-oriented criteria, have potential to catalyze private investment.

6. Leveraging blended finance models:

- Combining public funding with private investments in blended finance structures can bridge the financing gap.
- Innovative approaches like debt-for-nature swaps and biodiversity bonds can draw in private capital while maintaining strong public oversight.

7. Expanding market-based instruments:

- Market mechanisms, such as green and blue bonds, can be expanded to address biodiversity conservation needs beyond land restoration and pollution reduction.
- A shift towards ecosystem-level financing models could support a more holistic approach to biodiversity funding.

8. Harnessing public sector leadership for scalable solutions:

- While public sector financing currently dominates biodiversity finance, it serves as a critical foundation for scaling private investments.
- Public institutions can create enabling environments through regulatory frameworks, risk-sharing mechanisms, and technical support.

Combining TCforBE Deliverable 3.1 with outcomes from WP1 and 2

Combining the insights from the TCforBE deliverables, D1.1 and D2.1 of WP 1 and 2 respectively, with our work on biodiversity finance landscape in WP 3 underscores the evolving nature of biodiversity finance, characterized by a transition from traditional conservation financing to mechanisms that align with measurable nature-positive and equity outcomes. Building on the foundational metrics and frameworks outlined in the corresponding deliverables, as well as our earlier insights in this section on biodiversity finance landscape, a comprehensive narrative emerges regarding the strategic potential of financial instruments and levers.

Deliverables 1.1 and 2.1 already emphasize the criticality of biodiversity thresholds and governance, particularly in agroecological systems where nitrogen constraints and land-use impacts present both challenges and opportunities for financing. These insights align with the metrics-based approach outlined in our work package, where instruments like green bonds, sustainability-linked bonds, and biodiversity offsets are explored. The linkage between ecological thresholds and financial instruments offers a basis for integrating nature-positive outcomes into finance strategies. For instance, biodiversity-linked loans and outcome-based payments, underpinned by metrics such as nitrogen reduction or habitat restoration, directly connect ecological performance with financial incentives.

We further refine this approach by exploring the role of market-based instruments and regulatory alignment, emphasizing the effectiveness of hybrid models like blended finance. These models integrate public and private capital, mitigating risks while promoting investment in biodiversity-enhancing activities. The inclusion of biodiversity metrics such as those developed in the BiodivA model and their integration into the European Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS) provides a quantitative backbone for these instruments, facilitating their alignment with broader sustainability and regulatory frameworks.

The reports collectively highlight the transformative potential of biodiversity credits, particularly those integrating carbon and biodiversity co-benefits. Such instruments not only address the ecological dimensions of biodiversity loss but also create marketable assets that incentivize private sector participation. This duality is particularly effective in achieving equity outcomes, as demonstrated by mechanisms like Payments for Ecosystem Services (PES). PES schemes, when designed to incorporate contextual equity principles, ensure that financial benefits are equitably distributed, particularly to marginalized stakeholders such as smallholder farmers in biodiversity-sensitive regions.

Additionally, the reports underscore the importance of strategic policy alignment and governance. The integration of biodiversity finance into overarching policy frameworks, such as the EU Green Deal and Farm to Fork strategy, reflects a shift towards systemic change. This alignment is critical for addressing structural barriers and enabling the scalability of biodiversity-positive financial instruments.

The combined findings of the TCforBE deliverables of WP 1, 2, and 3 articulate a clear trajectory for biodiversity finance, emphasizing the symbiotic relationship between nature-positive outcomes and equity. By leveraging innovative instruments, aligning with robust metrics, and embedding equity considerations, the biodiversity finance landscape can move towards a transformative paradigm that balances ecological imperatives with economic and social equity. This integrated approach not only bridges existing funding gaps but also ensures that financial mechanisms contribute substantively to reversing biodiversity loss and fostering long-term sustainability.

For a detailed combination of the key insights, please see table 13.

Key Insight/Topic	Relevance in D1.1	Relevance in D2.1	Relevance in D3.1
Nitrogen Constraints and Biodiversity Thresholds	Highlights nitrogen as a critical ecological threshold influencing biodiversity	informs precision agriculture financing.	Extends ecological constraints to policy challenges, e.g., subsidy redesign for sustainable practices. Integrates nitrogen metrics into EU sustainability disclosures.
Biodiversity Metrics for Financing	Develops BiodivA metrics for evaluating biodiversity impacts, e.g., crop diversity, nutrient runoff.	Suggests expanded application of metrics in international biodiversity finance initiatives.	Aligns with ESRS metrics for biodiversity finance accountability.
Biodiversity Finance Instruments	Explores the role of agroecological financing for biodiversity-friendly practices.	Introduces biodiversity bonds and performance-based grants.	Details instruments like green bonds, biodiversity offsets, and sustainability-linked loans.
Governance and Policy Alignment	Discusses governance challenges in implementing biodiversity thresholds in agriculture.	Explores telecoupled governance for international biodiversity impacts.	Explores EU policy instruments, e.g., Taxonomy Regulation, SFDR.
Blended Finance and Risk Mitigation	Links innovative financing to ecosystem restoration.	Focuses on the combination of philanthropic	Discusses operationalization of blended finance models.

Key Insight/Topic	Relevance in D1.1	Relevance in D2.1	Relevance in D3.1
		and private investments.	
Equity Considerations in PES	Stresses the importance of equitable funding in smallholder adoption of practices.	Discusses procedural equity in biodiversity financing models.	Aligns PES design with EU Green Deal equity goals.
Carbon-Biodiversity Co-Benefits	Highlights opportunities for co-benefits in agroforestry projects.	Emphasizes financing for projects that integrate climate and biodiversity benefits.	Explores biodiversity-positive credits for EU carbon market integration.
Market-Based Mechanisms	Emphasizes the need for integrating local actors in market-based schemes.	Links PES to broader market opportunities for agroecological integration.	Analyzes market-based instruments for biodiversity under EU regulations.
EU Green Deal and Strategic Frameworks	Mentions the importance of governance in agroecological strategies.	Analyzes synergies with Farm to Fork strategy and EU taxonomy.	Provides detailed analysis of EU strategies for biodiversity finance.

Table 13: Combined insights from TCforBE workpackages

Combining the insights of these three WPs, nuanced perspectives on the effectiveness, design, and implementation of financial instruments as we introduced earlier on in the section emerge. Below, key outcomes of this integration are articulated:

Governance complexity and telecoupled frameworks

The telecoupled governance approach from D2.1 addresses cross-border impacts and interdependencies, offering a critical expansion of D3.1's governance-oriented recommendations. While D3.1 focuses on the EU-specific regulatory landscape, D2.1's insights reveal gaps in addressing the global implications of biodiversity finance. These frameworks suggest that instruments such as biodiversity bonds and sustainability-linked loans must account for governance disparities across regions to avoid unintended consequences and maximize effectiveness.

Blended finance: optimizing public-private collaboration

Both D2.1 and D3.1 highlight blended finance as a transformative model. D2.1 expands on the conditions under which blended finance is most effective, emphasizing the strategic use of public and philanthropic capital to reduce risks and attract private investments. This aligns with D3.1's exploration of hybrid financing models but adds a layer of operational clarity, demonstrating how targeted de-risking strategies can mobilize greater private sector participation in biodiversity-positive initiatives.

Equity-driven payments for ecosystem services

D2.1's detailed analysis of Payments for Ecosystem Services (PES) mechanisms refines D3.1's broader discussion by addressing the socio-economic dimensions of equity. Procedural and distributive equity are identified as critical to the success of PES schemes, ensuring that marginalized stakeholders, such as smallholder farmers, receive fair benefits and are actively involved in decision-

making. Incorporating these principles into the PES framework within D3.1 strengthens its alignment with both nature-positive and equitable outcomes.

Sector-specific interventions and metrics

D2.1 provides granular insights into sectoral interventions, particularly in agriculture, that complement D3.1's biodiversity finance instruments. For example, the promotion of regenerative agriculture and sustainable nutrient management can be directly tied to the metrics-based accountability systems described in D3.1. These connections demonstrate how sector-specific practices can inform and enhance the operationalization of biodiversity-linked financial instruments.

Carbon-biodiversity market synergies

Both deliverables recognize the potential of integrating biodiversity co-benefits into carbon markets. D2.1 delves deeper into the practical challenges of such integration, highlighting the need for standardized valuation methodologies and metrics. These insights address a critical gap in D3.1's discussion, providing actionable steps to enhance the marketability and impact of carbon-biodiversity credits.

Monitoring, reporting, and impact assessment

D2.1's emphasis on robust monitoring frameworks complements D3.1's reliance on metrics and indicators. It identifies gaps in data availability and quality, particularly regarding biodiversity loss drivers like invasive species. Incorporating these findings into D3.1 would enhance the precision and reliability of financial instruments, ensuring that their ecological and social impacts are effectively measured and reported.

Connecting to the model form deliverable 1.1

The integration of insights from Deliverable 1.1 into the biodiversity finance model presented in Deliverable 3.1 provides essential ecological underpinnings that enhance the operational design and implementation of financial instruments. D1.1 emphasizes the significance of ecological thresholds, such as nitrogen constraints and habitat connectivity, which can serve as critical benchmarks for biodiversity-linked financial mechanisms. Incorporating these thresholds into instruments like sustainability-linked bonds and outcome-based payments allows for a more targeted approach, directly incentivizing reductions in harmful practices and the adoption of biodiversity-positive interventions.

Furthermore, the BiodivA model introduced in D1.1 offers localized and scalable metrics, such as those for crop diversity and nutrient runoff, that align seamlessly with the accountability frameworks outlined in D3.1. These metrics not only strengthen the ecological rigor of financial instruments but also provide a mechanism for continuous monitoring and adaptive management. By integrating D1.1's granular agroecological insights, particularly its focus on sector-specific practices like regenerative agriculture, the finance model can refine its strategies to address context-specific biodiversity challenges effectively.

D1.1 also underscores the dynamic interactions between agricultural systems and biodiversity, advocating for financing mechanisms that adapt in response to real-time ecological feedback. This adaptability could be embedded into the financial model through dynamic scoring systems or interest-rate adjustments linked to ecological performance metrics. Lastly, D1.1 highlights the importance of engaging local stakeholders in the design and implementation of finance instruments, ensuring that interventions are both socially inclusive and ecologically grounded. These contributions not only bridge existing gaps in the biodiversity finance landscape but also position the model to achieve robust nature-positive and equitable outcomes.

Implications for Agrifood Producers (Telecoupling)

- 1. Alignment with Biodiversity and Sustainability Goals:** Agrifood producers in biodiversity-rich regions increasingly operate under pressure to comply with sustainability standards

driven by consumer demand, global frameworks (e.g., EU Green Deal, 30x30 target), and corporate commitments. The financing models, such as Payments for Ecosystem Services (PES) and incentives for regenerative agriculture, offer producers opportunities to align their operations with biodiversity-positive practices while accessing new funding streams. For example, PES schemes like those in Cuba provide financial compensation to producers maintaining forests or adopting low-carbon farming, enabling them to diversify income sources.

- 2. Market Differentiation and Access:** Producers who adopt biodiversity-friendly practices can gain access to premium markets. Certification schemes tied to nature-positive outcomes, as seen in South Africa's private land stewardship, enable producers to differentiate their products and meet the increasing demand for sustainable goods from global consumers.
- 3. Risks of Exclusion and Overburdening:** However, the financial models require significant upfront investments, knowledge, and capacity, which smallholder farmers in telecoupled regions often lack. Without targeted support, such as microfinance or capacity-building initiatives, smaller producers may struggle to meet biodiversity standards, risking exclusion from value chains dominated by larger, well-resourced entities.
- 4. Dependency on Consumer-Country Policies:** The emphasis on telecoupled governance frameworks means that agrifood producers in the Global South are often subject to policies shaped by consumer countries, such as the EU's Farm to Fork Strategy. While these policies aim to reduce the biodiversity footprint of EU imports, they can impose additional compliance costs on producers. To mitigate this, financial models must include mechanisms to ensure fair cost-sharing between consumer-country stakeholders (e.g., importers) and producers.

Implications for Equity Considerations

- 1. Distributive Equity:** Financial mechanisms like PES or biodiversity-linked loans must ensure equitable distribution of costs and benefits among stakeholders. Producers in the Global South often bear the environmental and social costs of biodiversity loss caused by global consumer demand. By integrating equity considerations into these mechanisms, such as fair compensation or subsidies, producers can be fairly remunerated for adopting biodiversity-positive practices.
- 2. Procedural Equity:** The design and implementation of financing schemes must actively involve producers, particularly smallholders and marginalized groups, in decision-making processes. As highlighted in D2.1, procedural equity ensures that producers have a voice in shaping policies and mechanisms that directly impact their livelihoods, fostering inclusivity and legitimacy.
- 3. Contextual Equity:** The playing field is rarely level; structural barriers such as limited access to financing, technical knowledge, and land tenure rights disproportionately affect smallholders and Indigenous communities. Financing mechanisms must address these pre-existing conditions by offering tailored support, such as capacity-building programs or preferential access to financial instruments, ensuring that vulnerable groups are not left behind.
- 4. Balancing Power Asymmetries:** Telecoupled value chains are often characterized by power imbalances between producers in the Global South and buyers or policymakers in consumer countries. Innovative financial solutions that prioritize equity can help shift some of this power by empowering producers to negotiate better terms, access global markets, and derive greater benefits from their participation in sustainable value chains.

For agrifood producers in telecoupled systems, the emergence of biodiversity finance mechanisms represents both opportunities and challenges. While they offer access to new funding and markets, producers often face the risk of marginalization due to the demands of compliance. Equity must be at the heart of these mechanisms, ensuring that benefits are distributed fairly, voices are heard, and barriers are addressed. By integrating equity principles into biodiversity finance, these solutions can drive transformative change not only for biodiversity but also for the livelihoods and rights of producers, creating a more balanced and sustainable global agrifood system.

Conclusion and Key Recommendations

The report reveals a dynamic global and EU biodiversity policy and finance landscape {Balachander, 2022 #391}, striving to contribute to mitigate biodiversity loss. However, despite significant advancements in both policy and finance mechanisms, this study highlights the substantial gap between current status and efforts to truly effect change. For example, the EU, through strategic frameworks and legislative measures, has integrated biodiversity considerations into a cohesive policy agenda, aiming to pivot from reactive measures to a more integrated, proactive approach. However, the effectiveness of these actions over time will be contingent upon a clear, coordinated strategy that not only addresses immediate conservation needs but also ensures long-term sustainability and resilience, as well as compliance.

Based on the aggregated insights from the report, several key recommendations emerge as pathways to enhance the impact and reach of biodiversity finance:

1. Increase synergy between public and private financing:

There is a clear need for enhancing the interaction between public and private financing mechanisms. Leveraging public funds to de-risk private investments can catalyze more substantial flows of private capital into biodiversity projects.

2. Expand and diversify financial instruments:

Innovation in financial products is crucial. Beyond the traditional instruments such as impact investing there should be an exploration of hybrid financial tools such as blended finance, which can combine grants with loans and equity from private and public sources to fund biodiversity initiatives effectively (e.g., PES or sustainability linked bonds).

3. Strengthen global and EU regulatory Frameworks:

To ensure that financial flows are both substantial and sustainable, robust regulatory frameworks must be established on global and regional levels. These frameworks should not only incentivize investments in biodiversity-positive projects but also penalize non-compliance and harmful practices effectively. Work package 2, particularly deliverable 2.1 which critically reviews the content of global biodiversity initiatives, offers useful complementary insights to enable this.

4. Foster global and regional partnerships:

Enhancing international cooperation can aid in pooling resources, sharing knowledge, and harmonizing actions across borders. Such partnerships are essential to tackle global biodiversity challenges, given the transnational nature of many ecological networks.

5. Enhance Transparency and accountability:

There should be a greater emphasis on monitoring and reporting mechanisms to track the impact of investments and ensure accountability. Implementing comprehensive disclosure requirements related to biodiversity impacts can provide clarity and confidence to investors and stakeholders alike.

Implementing these recommendations requires a concerted effort from all sectors involved, from governments and international bodies to private investors and civil society. Only through a unified approach can we hope to secure the financial investment needed to preserve the planet's biodiversity for future generations. The role of strategic actions, especially in aligning financial tools and regulatory measures with conservation goals, cannot be overstated in driving forward a sustainable agenda for biodiversity finance.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Global Biodiversity Initiatives

Initiatives	Abbreviation	Non-Profit / Profit	Head-quarter	year of introduction	biodiversity theory	Scope of application	Target audience	link
International Union for Conservation of Nature	IUCN	NGO	Switzerland	1948	extinction accounting	awareness & intergovernmental	public, private and non-governmental organizations	https://www.iucn.org/our-work/biodiversity
Global Reporting Initiative	GRI	Profit	USA	1997	other	standard setter	corporates	https://www.globalreporting.org/
Science-based targets for nature	SBTN	NPO	UK	2015	natural capital	standard setter	corporates	https://sciencebasedtargetsnetwork.org/
Capitals Coalition	CC	Association	Netherlands	2007	natural capital	standard setter	corporates	https://capitalscoalition.org/
Finance for biodiversity pledge	FfB	Association	n.a.	2021	ecosystem services	financing	financial institutions	https://www.financeforbiodiversity.org/
Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures	TNFD	NPO	USA	2020	other	standard setter	corporates	https://tnfd.global/
Sustainable Development Goals	SDGs	intergovernmental	USA	2012	other	awareness & intergovernmental	public, private and non-governmental organizations	https://sdgs.un.org/goals
Natural Capital finance alliance	NCAFA	intergovernmental	USA	2012	natural capital	standard setter	financial institutions	https://naturalcapital.finance/
World business council for sustainable development	WBCSD	intergovernmental	Switzerland	1995	ecosystem services	standard setter	corporates	https://www.wbcsd.org/
Business for Nature	BfN	Association	USA	2019	natural capital	awareness & intergovernmental	corporates	https://www.businessfornature.org/
The Convention on Biological Diversity	CBD	intergovernmental	Canada	1992	ecosystem services	awareness & intergovernmental	public, private and non-governmental organizations	https://www.cbd.int/convention/
Intergovernmental Science-Policy	IPBES	intergovernmental	Germany	2012	extinction accounting	awareness & intergovernmental	public, private and non-governmental organizations	https://www.ipbes.net/

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Initiatives	Abbreviation	Non-Profit / Profit	Head-quarter	year of introduction	biodiversity theory	Scope of application	Target audience	link
Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services								
Carbon Disclosure Project	CDP	NPO	UK	2000	other	data providers	corporates	https://www.cdp.net/en
World Benchmarking Alliance	WBA	NPO	Netherlands	2018	ecosystem services	data providers	public, private and non-governmental organizations	https://www.worldbenchmarkingalliance.org/
Accountability Accelerator	GCAA	NPO	UK	2022	other	data providers	corporates	https://globalcommonsalliance.org/alliance-projects/accountability-accelerator/
Ceres	Ceres	NPO	USA	1989	other	financing	financial institutions	https://www.ceres.org/
Planet Tracker	Planet Tracker	NPO	UK	2018	natural capital	financing	financial institutions	https://planet-tracker.org/
Share Action	Share Action	NPO	UK	2005	other	financing	financial institutions	https://shareaction.org/
Partnership for Biodiversity Accounting Financials	PBAF	NPO	Netherlands	2019	extinction accounting	standard setter	financial institutions	https://pbafglobal.com/
International Integrated Reporting Council	IIRC	NPO	USA	2013	natural capital	standard setter	corporates	https://www.integratedreporting.org/the-iirc-2/

Table 14: Appendix 1: International policy initiatives

Appendix 2: EU Biodiversity Policy Landscape

Appendix 2a: Strategic Frameworks and Legislations

Nr	Name of policy	Abbrv.	year of adoption	Date of publication	Publication type	Directorate-General	Motivator	if Driver - which	Com-ments	Link
1	EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030		2020	20/05/2020	Communication	DG Environment	Governance			https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1590574123338&uri=CELEX%3A52020DC0380
2	Nature restoration Regulation		2022	22/06/2022	Proposal	DG Environment	Protection		Proposal	https://environment.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2022-06/Proposal%20for%20a%20Regulation%20on%20nature%20restoration.pdf
3	Birds Directive		2009	30/11/2009	Directive	DG Environment	Protection			https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32009L0147&from=EN
4	Habitats Directive	HD	1992	21/05/1992	Directive	DG Environment	Protection			https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:31992L0043&from=EN
5	EU Pollinators Initiative		2023	24/01/2023	Communication	DG Environment	Restoration		Revision from 2018	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52023DC0035&from=EN
6	New EU Forest Strategy for 2030		2021	16/07/2021	Communication	DG Environment	Protection			https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:0d918e07-e610-11eb-a1a5-01aa75ed71a1.0001.02/DOC_1&format=PDF
7	Timber Regulation	EUTR	2010	20/10/2010	Regulation	DG Environment	Driver minimization	direct exploitation of organisms	Proposal from 2021	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32010R0995&from=EN
8	Sustainable Europe Investment Plan		2020	14/01/2020	Communication	DG Financial Stability, Financial Services and Capital Markets Union	Financing			https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52020DC0021&from=EN
9	Revision of the EU action plan against wildlife trafficking		2022	09/11/2022	Communication	DG Environment	Driver minimization	direct exploitation of organisms		https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52022DC0581&from=EN
10	Sustainable use of pesticides Directive	SUD	2009	21/10/2009	Directive	DG Health and Food Safety	Driver minimization	pollution	Proposal from 2022	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32009L0128&from=EN
11	Farm to Fork Strategy		2020	20/05/2020	Communication	DG Health and Food Safety	Driver minimization	pollution		https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:ea0f9f73-9ab2-11ea-9d2d-01aa75ed71a1.0001.02/DOC_1&format=PDF

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Nr	Name of policy	Abbrev.	year of adoption	Date of publication	Publication type	Directorate-General	Motivator	if Driver - which	Comments	Link
12	EU Soil Strategy for 2030		2021	17/11/2021	Communication	DG Environment	Restoration			https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52021DC0699&from=EN
13	Action Plan for the development of organic production		2021	19/04/2021	Communication	DG Agriculture and Rural Development	Driver minimization	pollution		https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:13dc912c-a1a5-11eb-b85c-01aa75ed71a1.0003.02/DOC_1&format=PDF
14	Organic production and labelling		2018	30/05/2018	Regulation	DG Agriculture and Rural Development	Support			https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32018R0848&from=EN
15	Food information to consumers	FIC	2011	25/10/2011	Regulation	DG Health and Food Safety	Support		Proposal still in work	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32011R1169&from=EN
16	Land use, land use change and forestry Regulation	LULUCF	2018	30/05/2018	Regulation	DG Climate Action	Driver minimization	land- and sea-use change	Commission delegated Regulations 2020	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32018R0841&from=EN
17	Taxonomy Regulation		2020	18/06/2020	Regulation	DG Financial Stability, Financial Services and Capital Markets Union	Financing			https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32020R0852&from=EN
18	Sustainability-related disclosures in the financial services sector	SFDR	2019	27/11/2019	Regulation	DG Financial Stability, Financial Services and Capital Markets Union	Financing			https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32019R2088&from=EN
19	Corporate sustainability reporting Directive	CSRD	2022	14/12/2022	Directive	DG Financial Stability, Financial Services and Capital Markets Union	Financing		Standards	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32022L2464&from=EN
20	Invasive Alien Species	IAS	2014	22/10/2014	Regulation	DG Environment	Driver minimization	invasive alien species		https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32014R1143&from=EN
21	Use of Energy from renewable sources	RED II	2018	11/12/2018	Directive	DG Energy	Driver minimization	direct exploitation of organisms		https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32018L2001&from=de
22	Regulation on financing the CAP	CAP	2021	02/12/2021	Regulation	DG Agriculture and Rural Development	Financing		CAP	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32021R2116&from=EN
23	CAP strategic plan Regulation	CAP	2021	02/12/2021	Regulation	DG Agriculture and Rural Development	Protection		CAP	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32021R2115&from=EN

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Nr	Name of policy	Abbrev.	year of adoption	Date of publication	Publication type	Directorate-General	Motivator	if Driver - which	Com-ments	Link
24	Common Market Organisation regulation	CAP	2021	02/12/2021	Regulation	DG Agriculture and Rural Development	Governance		CAP	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32021R2117&from=EN
25	Action Plan: Towards Zero Pollution for Air, Water and Soil		2021	12/05/2021	Communication	DG Environment	Driver minimization	pollution		https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:a1c34a56-b314-11eb-8aca-01aa75ed71a1.0001.02/DOC_1&format=PDF
26	EU Common Fisheries Policy	CFP	2013	11/12/2013	Regulation	DG Maritime Affairs and Fisheries	Driver minimization	direct exploitation of organisms		https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32013R1380&from=EN
27	Marine Strategy Framework Directive	MSFD	2008	17/06/2008	Directive	DG Environment	Protection			https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32008L0056&from=EN
28	Water Framework Directive	WFD	2000	23/10/2000	Directive	DG Environment	Protection			https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:5c835afb-2ec6-4577-bdf8-756d3d694eeb.0004.02/DOC_1&format=PDF
29	New Circular Economy Action Plan		2020	11/03/2020	Communication	DG Environment	Driver minimization	climate change		https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:9903b325-6388-11ea-b735-01aa75ed71a1.0017.02/DOC_1&format=PDF
30	European green bond Regulation		2021	06/07/2021	Proposal	DG Financial Stability, Financial Services and Capital Markets Union	Financing		Proposal, EC agreed on the proposal on 28.2.23	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:e77212e8-df07-11eb-895a-01aa75ed71a1.0001.02/DOC_1&format=PDF
31	European Green Deal		2019	11/12/2019	Communication	DG for Communication	Governance			

Table 15: Appendix 2a: EU Strategic frameworks and legislations

Appendix 2b: Disclosure Frameworks, Indicators, and Metrics

	TNFD	GRI	CSRD/ESRS	Taxonomy Regulation	SFDR	ISSB/IFRS	NCP	SBTN	CDP	Green Bond Standard	
General Information	released in	2023	2000	2022	2020	2019	2023	2016	2023	2000	2023
	voluntary/mandatory	Voluntary	Voluntary	Mandatory	Mandatory	Mandatory	Voluntary	Voluntary	Voluntary	Voluntary	Voluntary
	target audience	Corporates and financial institutions	Businesses, financial institutions and other organizations	Corporates, banks, insurance companies	Companies, financial market participants	Financial advisors, financial market participants, insurance companies, pension funds	Businesses and financial institutions	Businesses and financial institutions	Businesses and financial institutions	Companies, cities, states and regions	Issuers of bonds that are made available to investors in the European Union
Key terms and definitions	biodiversity	The variability among living organisms from all sources, including, inter alia, terrestrial, marine and other aquatic ecosystems and the ecological complexes of which they are part; this includes diversity within species, between species and of ecosystems. (UN, 1992)	The variability of organisms living in terrestrial, marine, and aquatic ecosystems, as well as the ecological complexes they form. It comprises the genetic diversity within species, the variety of species in an area, and the distinct features of entire ecosystems.(UN, 1992)	The variability among living organisms from all sources including, inter alia, terrestrial, freshwater, marine and other aquatic ecosystems and the ecological complexes of which they are part.(UN, 1992)	The variability among living organisms arising from all sources including terrestrial, marine and other aquatic ecosystems and the ecological complexes of which they are part and includes diversity within species, between species and of ecosystems. (UN, 1992)	N/A	N/A	The variability among living organisms from all sources including, inter alia, terrestrial, marine, and other aquatic ecosystems and the ecological complexes of which they are part; this includes diversity within species, between species, and of ecosystems. (UN, 1992)	The variability among living organisms from all sources, including, inter alia, terrestrial, marine, and other aquatic ecosystems and the ecological complexes of which they are part; this includes diversity within species, between species, and of ecosystems. (UN, 1992)	The biological diversity of flora and fauna species on Earth, a complex web of life that underpins the natural life processes on the planet.	N/A
	realm	Major components of the living, natural world that differ fundamentally in ecosystem organization	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

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	TNFD	GRI	CSRD/ESRS	Taxonomy Regulation	SFDR	ISSB/IFRS	NCP	SBTN	CDP	Green Bond Standard
	and function: terrestrial (land), freshwater, marine (ocean), subterranean and atmospheric. The TNFD's framework is based on four realms - land, freshwater, ocean and atmosphere. The subterranean realm is included within the land, freshwater and ocean realms.									
biome	Global-scale zones, generally defined by the type of plant life that they support in response to average rainfall and temperature patterns e.g. tundra, coral reefs or savannas. For the purpose of metrics, biomes are defined in the IUCN Global Ecosystem Typology as the component of a realm united by a few common major ecological drivers that	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

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	TNFD	GRI	CSRD/ESRS	Taxonomy Regulation	SFDR	ISSB/IFRS	NCP	SBTN	CDP	Green Bond Standard
	regulate major ecological functions. Biomes are derived from the top down by subdivision of realms.									
ecosystem	A dynamic complex of plant, animal and microorganism communities and the non-living environment, interacting as a functional unit.	N/A	A dynamic complex of plant, animal and micro-organism communities and their non-living environment interacting as a functional unit. A typology of ecosystems is provided by the IUCN Global Ecosystem Typology 2.0.	A dynamic complex of plant, animal, and micro-organism communities and their non-living environment interacting as a functional unit	N/A	N/A	A dynamic complex of plants, animals, and microorganisms, and their non-living environment, interacting as a functional unit. Examples include deserts, coral reefs, wetlands, and rainforests (MA 2005a). Ecosystems are part of natural capital.	A dynamic complex of plant, animal, and microorganism communities and the non-living environment interacting as a functional unit. Within this definition, the term "unit" relies on the identification of a distinct function as well as a "dynamic" grouping of biotic and abiotic factors. When using an ecosystem approach to conservation, the United Nations Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) suggests an ecosystem	N/A	N/A

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	TNFD	GRI	CSRD/ESRS	Taxonomy Regulation	SFDR	ISSB/IFRS	NCP	SBTN	CDP	Green Bond Standard
								can refer to any functioning unit, regardless of scale. Thus, the term is not necessarily synonymous with “biome” or “ecological zone” and is better determined by the problem that is being addressed		
ecosystem services	The contributions of ecosystems to the benefits that are used in economic and other human activity. (based on UN SEEA)	N/A	The contributions of ecosystems to the benefits that are used in economic and other human activity, respectively the benefits people obtain from ecosystems. In the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, ecosystem services can be divided into supporting, regulating, provisioning and cultural. The Common International Classification of Ecosystem	The direct and indirect contributions of ecosystems to the economic, social, cultural and other benefits that people derive from those ecosystems	N/A	N/A	The most widely used definition of ecosystem services is from the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (MA 2005a): “the benefits people obtain from ecosystems”.	N/A	N/A	N/A

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	TNFD	GRI	CSRD/ESRS	Taxonomy Regulation	SFDR	ISSB/IFRS	NCP	SBTN	CDP	Green Bond Standard
			Services (CICES) classifies types of ecosystems services.							
habitat	The area, characterised by its abiotic and biotic properties, that is habitable by a particular species.	N/A	The place or type of site where an organism or population naturally occurs. Also used to mean the environmental attributes required by a particular species or its ecological niche.	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
species	A fundamental category for the classification and description of organisms, defined in various ways but typically on the basis of reproductive capacity; i.e. the members of a species can reproduce with each other to produce fertile offspring but cannot do so with individuals outside the species.	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

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	TNFD	GRI	CSRD/ESRS	Taxonomy Regulation	SFDR	ISSB/IFRS	NCP	SBTN	CDP	Green Bond Standard
impacts	<p>Changes in the state of nature (quality or quantity), which may result in changes to the capacity of nature to provide social and economic functions. Impacts can be positive or negative. They can be the result of an organization's or another party's actions and can be direct, indirect or cumulative. A single impact driver may be associated with multiple impacts.</p>	<p>The effect the organization has or could have on the economy, environment, and people, including on their human rights, which in turn can indicate its contribution (negative or positive) to sustainable development</p>	<p>The effect the undertaking has or could have on the environment and people, including effects on their human rights, as a result of the undertaking's activities or business relationships. The impacts can be actual or potential, negative or positive, short-term or long-term time horizons, intended or unintended, and reversible or irreversible. Impacts indicate the undertaking's contribution, negative or positive, to sustainable development.</p>	N/A	N/A	<p>A change in the diversity of ecosystems and/or species that may take place because of business activities. Changes to the state of ecosystems (e.g. extent and condition/integrity) and species (e.g. habitat, population size) can be used to signal changes in biodiversity.</p>	<p>The negative or positive effect of business activity on natural capital.</p>	<p>Can be positive or negative contributions of a company or other actor toward the state of nature, including pollution of air, water, or soil; fragmentation or disruption of ecosystems and habitats for nonhuman species; and alteration of ecosystem processes.</p>	N/A	N/A

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	TNFD	GRI	CSRD/ESRS	Taxonomy Regulation	SFDR	ISSB/IFRS	NCP	SBTN	CDP	Green Bond Standard
dependencies	Aspects of environmental assets and ecosystem services that a person or an organization relies on to function. A company's business model, for example, may be dependent on the ecosystem services of water flow, water quality regulation and the regulation of hazards like fires and floods; provision of suitable habitat for pollinators, who in turn provide a service directly to economies; and carbon sequestration.	N/A	Dependency is the result of the undertaking relying on biodiversity and/or ecosystems within its business model and/or conduct of business.	N/A	N/A	The reliance on or use of biodiversity, including biological resources (e.g. materials, liquids, genetic resources) from both	A business reliance on or use of natural capital.	Aspects of nature's contributions to people that a person or organization relies on to function, including water flow and quality regulation; regulation of hazards like fires and floods; pollination; carbon sequestration.	N/A	N/A
risks	Potential threats posed to an organisation linked to its and other organisations' dependencies on nature and nature impacts. These can derive from physical, transition and systemic risks.	N/A	Uncertain environmental, social or governance events or conditions that, if they occur, could cause a potential material negative effect on the undertaking's business model, strategy and sustainability strategy, its	N/A	An environmental, social or governance event or condition that, if it occurs, could cause an actual or a potential material negative impact on the value of the investment;	Climate-related risks refers to the potential negative effects of climate change on an entity. These risks are categorised as climate-related physical risks and climate-related	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

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	TNFD	GRI	CSRD/ESRS	Taxonomy Regulation	SFDR	ISSB/IFRS	NCP	SBTN	CDP	Green Bond Standard
			capability to achieve its goals and targets and to create value, and therefore may influence its decisions and those of its business relationships with regard to sustainability matters. Like any other risks, sustainability related risks are the combination of an impact's magnitude and the probability of occurrence.			transition risks.				
opportunities	Activities that create positive outcomes for organisations and nature by avoiding or reducing impact on nature or contributing to its restoration.	N/A	Uncertain environmental, social or governance events or conditions that, if they occur, could cause a potential material positive effect on the undertaking's business model, strategy, its capability to achieve its goals and targets and to create value, and therefore may influence its decisions	N/A	N/A	Climate-related opportunities refers to the potential positive effects arising from climate change for an entity. Efforts to mitigate and adapt to climate change can produce climate related opportunities for an entity.	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

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	TNFD	GRI	CSRD/ESRS	Taxonomy Regulation	SFDR	ISSB/IFRS	NCP	SBTN	CDP	Green Bond Standard
			and those of its business relationship partners with regards to sustainability matters. Like any other opportunity, sustainability-related opportunities are measured as a combination of an impact's magnitude and the probability of occurrence.							
materiality	Double materiality has two dimensions, namely: impact materiality and financial materiality (EFRAG). Impact materiality refers to information on the organization's most significant impacts on the economy, environment, and people, including impacts on their human rights (GRI). Financial materiality should be aligned with ISSB.	The organization prioritizes reporting on those topics that represent its most significant impacts on the economy, environment, and people, including impacts on their human rights.	A sustainability matter is material if it meets the definition of impact materiality, financial materiality, or both. A sustainability matter is material from a financial perspective if it generates risks or opportunities that affect (or could reasonably be expected to affect) the undertaking's financial position, financial performance, cash flows,	N/A	N/A	Information is material if omitting, misstating or obscuring that information could reasonably be expected to influence decisions that primary users of general purpose financial reports make on the basis of those reports, which include financial statements and sustainability-related financial	An impact or dependency on natural capital is material if consideration of its value, as part of the set of information used for decision making, has the potential to alter that decision.	Double materiality is a concept which provides criteria for determination of whether a sustainability topic or information has to be included in the undertaking's sustainability report. Double materiality is the union (in mathematical terms, i.e. union of two sets, not intersection) of impact materiality and financial	N/A	N/A

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TNFD	GRI	CSRD/ESRS	Taxonomy Regulation	SFDR	ISSB/IFRS	NCP	SBTN	CDP	Green Bond Standard
		access to finance or cost of capital over the short, medium or long term. A sustainability matter is material from an impact perspective when it pertains to the undertaking's material actual or potential, positive or negative impacts on people or the environment over the short-, medium- and long-term. A material sustainability matter from an impact perspective includes impacts connected with the undertaking's own operations and upstream and downstream value chain, including through its products and services, as well as through its business relationships.			disclosures and which provide information about a specific reporting entity.		materiality. A sustainability topic or information meets therefore the criteria of double materiality if it is material from the impact perspective or from the financial perspective or from both of these two perspectives. A sustainability topic or information is material from an impact perspective if the undertaking is connected to actual or potential significant impacts on people or the environment and is related to the sustainability topic over the short, medium or long term. This includes impacts directly caused or contributed		

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TNFD	GRI	CSRD/ESRS	Taxonomy Regulation	SFDR	ISSB/IFRS	NCP	SBTN	CDP	Green Bond Standard
							<p>to by the undertaking, and impacts which are otherwise directly linked to the undertaking's upstream and downstream value chain. A sustainability topic is material from a financial perspective if it triggers financial effects on undertakings, by generating risks or opportunities that influence or are likely to influence the future cash flows and therefore the enterprise value of the undertaking in the short, medium or long term but are not captured by financial reporting at the reporting date. (EFRAG)</p>		

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	TNFD	GRI	CSRD/ESRS	Taxonomy Regulation	SFDR	ISSB/IFRS	NCP	SBTN	CDP	Green Bond Standard	
Assessment and disclosure requirements	assessment and disclosure level	Entity level	Entity level	Entity level (parent & subsidiary)	Activity and entity level	product (fund category) and entity level (PAI)	Entity level (parent & subsidiary)	Entity level	Entity level	Entity level City level	Activity and product level
	assessment focus	dependencies, impacts, risks, and opportunities	Impacts on the economy, environment, and people	dependencies, impacts, risks, and opportunities	dependencies, impacts, risks, and opportunities	dependencies and risks	dependencies, impacts, risks, and opportunities	dependencies, impacts, (natural capital) risks, and (natural capital) opportunities	dependencies, impacts, risks, and opportunities	dependencies, impacts, risks, and opportunities	dependencies, impacts, risks, and opportunities
	assessment approach	LEAP approach: 1. Locate your interface with nature 2. Evaluate your dependencies and impacts on nature 3. Assess your nature-related risks and opportunities 4. Prepare to respond to, and report on, material nature-related issues, aligned with the TNFD's recommended disclosures	Four step approach: 1. Understand the organisation's context 2. Identify actual and potential impacts 3. Assess the significance of the impacts 4. Prioritise the most significant impacts to determine the material topics for reporting	LEAP approach: 1. Locate your interface with nature in your value chain 2. Evaluate your dependencies and impacts on nature 3. Assess your nature-related risks and opportunities 4. Prepare to respond to, and report on, material nature-related issues, aligned with the ESRS	Three step classification process: 1. Activity significantly contributes to at least one environmental objective; 2. Activity does no significant harm to any of the other five environmental objectives; 3. Activity complies with minimum safeguards	Three step classification process: 1. Does the fund have sustainable investment as its objective (Taxonomy aligned)? 2. Does the fund promote environmental and/or social characteristics? 3. Does the fund not promote environmental and/or social characteristics?	Three step approach: 1. Disclose sustainability-related risks and opportunities 2, Disclose information about climate-related risks and opportunities 3. Disclose impacts and dependencies on resources and relationships throughout entity's value chain.	Six step approach: 1. Define assessment objective 2. Define assessment scope 3. Determine impacts and dependencies 4. Measure impact drivers and/or dependencies 5. Measure changes in the state of natural capital 6. Value impacts and/or dependencies	Five step approach: 1. Assess impacts & dependencies 2. Interpret & prioritise key issues and locations 3. Measure, set & disclose targets aligned with planetary boundaries 4. Act (ARRRT) 5. Track progress toward targets	N/A	Classification process: 1. Determine whether proceeds are allocated to activities that classify as environmentally sustainable. 2. Determine whether proceeds contribute to the transformation of activities so they become environmentally sustainable.
	disclosure basis	Materiality	Materiality	Materiality	TSC thresholds, DNSH criteria and MSS	TSC thresholds, DNSH criteria and MSS	Materiality	Materiality	Materiality	N/A	TSC thresholds, DNSH criteria and MSS
	disclosure structure	Four-pillars	Modular system of interconnected standards	Four-pillars	Six pillars objectives	Three categories	Four-pillars		Two aspects	Sector and Topic Specific Modules	Six-pillars

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	TNFD	GRI	CSRD/ESRS	Taxonomy Regulation	SFDR	ISSB/IFRS	NCP	SBTN	CDP	Green Bond Standard
disclosure content	_Governance _Strategy _Risk management _Metrics and targets	_General disclosures _Material topics _Reasons for Omissions	_Governance, _Strategy _Management of impacts, risks and opportunities _Metrics and targets	proportional ity of taxonomy aligned activities in six environmen tal objectives: 1. climate change mitigation, 2. climate change adaptation, 3. sustainable use and protection of water and marine resources, 4. transition to a circular economy, 5. pollution prevention and control, 6. protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems	Proportional ity of products as in _Article 6 _Article 8 _Article 9	_Governance _Strategy _Risk managemen t _Metrics and targets	N/A	_Goals addressing biodiversity loss drivers across realms _Goals addressing state of nature across realms	_Identification, Assessment, and Management of Dependencies , Impacts, Risks and Opportunities _Disclosure of Dependencies , Risks, and Opportunities _Governance _Business Strategy _Climate change _Water _Forests _Biodiversity _Plastics	_General Information _Important Information _Environmental strategy and rationale _Intended allocation of bond proceeds _Environment al impact of bond proceeds _Informatio n on reporting _CapEx plan _Other
disclosure types	Qualitative and quantitative	Qualitative and quantitative	Qualitative and quantitative	Qualitative, quantitative, monetary	Qualitative, quantitative, monetary	Qualitative and quantitative	Qualitative, quantitative, monetary	Qualitative and quantitative	Qualitative and quantitative	Qualitative and quantitative
BA approach	Natural inventory, ecosystem	Natural inventory, ecosystem	Natural inventory, ecosystem	Natural inventory, ecosystem	Natural inventory, ecosystem	Natural inventory, ecosystem	Natural inventory, ecosystem	Natural inventory, ecosystem	Natural inventory, ecosystem	Natural inventory, ecosystem
connection to other frameworks	ISSB, IFRS, SBTN, EU Taxonomy	SBTN, TNFD	EU Taxonomy, CSRD, TNFD	SFDR, Green bond standard	EU Taxonomy, CSRD, ESRS	TNFD, TCFD, CDSB, GRI, ESRS	GRI	TCFD, TNFD, GRI, CSRD, CDP	ISSB	EU Taxonomy
sector guidance (y/n)	Draft	Yes	Draft	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	None

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	TNFD	GRI	CSRD/ESRS	Taxonomy Regulation	SFDR	ISSB/IFRS	NCP	SBTN	CDP	Green Bond Standard
sector guidance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> _Oil and gas _Metals and mining _Forestry and paper _Food and agriculture _Electric utilities and power generators _Chemicals _Biotechnology and pharmaceuticals _Aquaculture _Financial institutions 	<p>Group 1: Basic materials and needs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> _Oil and gas _Coal _Agriculture, aquaculture, and fishing _Mining _Food and beverages _Textiles and apparel _Banking _Insurance _Capital markets _Utilities _Renewable energy _Forestry _Metal processing <p>Group 2: Industrial</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> _Construction materials _Aerospace and defence _Automotive _Construction _Chemicals _Machinery and equipment _Pharmaceuticals _Electronics <p>Group 3: Transport, infrastructure and tourism</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> _Media and communication _Software _Real estate _Transportation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> _Oil and Gas _Coal, Quarries and Mining _Road Transport _Agriculture, Farming and Fisheries _Motor Vehicles _Energy Production and Utilities _Food and Beverages _Textiles, Accessories, Footwear and Jewellery 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Financial and non-financial undertakings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Financial undertakings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> _Consumer Goods _Extractives & Minerals Processing _Financials _Food & Beverage _Health Care _Infrastructure _Renewable Resources & Alternative Energy _Resource Transformation _Services _Technology & Communications _Transportation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> _Apparel _Food & Beverage Products _Finance Sector Supplement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> _Cities _Companies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> _Financial Services _Capital Goods _Metals & mining _Agricultural commodities _Cement _Real estate _Oil & gas _Transport OEMS – EPM _Transport services _Electric utilities _Food, beverages & tobacco _Construction _Coal _Chemicals _Steel _Transport OEMS _Paper & forestry 	<p>For those sectors which are not covered by the EU Taxonomy, there is a 15% of flexibility.</p>

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TNFD	GRI	CSRD/ESRS	Taxonomy Regulation	SFDR	ISSB/IFRS	NCP	SBTN	CDP	Green Bond Standard
	n infrastructure _Shipping _Trucking _Airlines _Trading, distribution, and logistics _Packaging _Hotels Group 4: Other services and light manufacturing _Educational services _Household durables _Managed health care _Medical equipment and services _Retail _Security services and correctional facilities _Restaurants _Commercial services _Non-profit organizations								

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	TNFD	GRI	CSRD/ESRS	Taxonomy Regulation	SFDR	ISSB/IFRS	NCP	SBTN	CDP	Green Bond Standard
scope of value chain	Direct operations, upstream and downstream (value chains and geographies in which the organisation operates)	Direct operations and upstream and downstream (downstream is optional in the GRI Biodiversity Standard)	Direct operations, upstream and downstream (In case there are associates or joint ventures (within equity method or proportionally consolidated) that are involved in the value chain (supplier) then this should be included in the report)	N/A	N/A	Direct operations, upstream and downstream	Direct operations, upstream and downstream	Direct operations, upstream and downstream (downstream may be covered in future releases)	Direct operations, upstream and some downstream	N/A
location specific data required (y/n)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
data granularity	Global, national, sub-national, regional, local, site	Global, national, sub-national, regional, local, site	National, sub-national, regional, local, site	Local	Local	Local	Local	National, sub-national, regional, local, site	National, sub-regional and local	Local
biodiversity data	_Species specific data _Ecosystem specific data _Genetic variation	_Species specific _Ecosystem specific _Genetic variation	_Species _Ecosystem _Land coverage _Genetic variation	_Species specific _Ecosystem specific _Genetic variation _Climate scenarios	N/A	N/A	_Ecosystem specific _Species specific _Genetic variation	_Species specific _Ecosystem specific _Genetic variation	_Ecosystem specific _Species specific _Genetic variation	N/A
specific indicators & metrics	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Flexible	Yes	Yes	N/A
most mentioned tools / databases	_SBTN target-setting tool _IBAT _Trase _LIFE Impact Index _Global Biodiversity Score _EXIOBASE	_ENCORE _SBTN Materiality Screening _IBAT _SBTN target-setting tool	_ENCORE _Common database on designated areas _World database of protected areas _Bioscope _Trase	N/A	N/A	_IBAT _The Agrobiodiversity Index _ENCORE _Trase Earth Tool _OHI+ _IPBES _SBTN _Natural	Biodiversity Navigation Tool (NCC)	_ENCORE _UNEP-WCMC Natural Capital Hotspots Map _Integrated Valuation of Ecosystem Services and	_BFC – Biodiversity Footprint Calculator _Biological Diversity Protocol _Bioscope _BNGC – Biodiversity _Net Gain	N/A

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TNFD	GRI	CSRD/ESRS	Taxonomy Regulation	SFDR	ISSB/IFRS	NCP	SBTN	CDP	Green Bond Standard
_Global Forest Watch		_WWF Risk Filter Suite _Globio model _EXIOBASE _IPCCC Climate Scenarios _Global Forest Watch _The Living Planet Database _The International Waterbird			Capital Protocol _The Transparent project _Align		Tradeoffs (InVEST) models _SwissRe Institute Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (BES) Index	Calculator _CBD – Global Biodiversity Framework _CBF – Corporate Biodiversity Footprint _ENCORE _F4B - Finance for Biodiversity [FS only] _GBS – Global Biodiversity Score _IBAT – Integrated Biodiversity Assessment Tool _LafargeHolcim _LIFE Key _Natural Capital Protocol _PBAF – Partnership for Biodiversity Accounting Financials [FS only] _PBF – Product Biodiversity Footprint _ReCiPe _SBTN materiality tool _WBCSD Corporate Ecosystem Services Review	

Table 16: Appendix 2b: Comparison of major global biodiversity measurement frameworks

Appendix 2c: Strategic Actions

Nr.	Title	Chef de File / DG	Area	Sub Area	GBF Target	Cluster	Driver	Linked Legislation	Affected group
1	Commission guidance for identifying and designating additional protected areas, and appropriate management planning	ENV	Coherent Network of Protected Areas		1, 2, 3	Protection		EU Biodiversity Strategy	regulators
2	Complete the designation of Natura 2000 Sites, including the necessary designations of marine sites	ENV	Coherent Network of Protected Areas		1, 2, 3	Protection		Natura 2000	regulators
3	Coordinate with Member States nature protection actions in the framework of the biogeographical regions and regional sea conventions	ENV	Coherent Network of Protected Areas		1, 2, 3	Protection			regulators
4	Possible adjustment of the reporting format for nationally designated protected areas	EEA	Coherent Network of Protected Areas		1, 2, 3	Protection			research
5	Progress significantly in legally designating new protected areas and integrating ecological corridors	ENV	Coherent Network of Protected Areas		1, 2, 3	Protection			regulators
6	Commission assessment of progress to the 2030 targets on protected areas, and of whether additional action is needed	ENV	Coherent Network of Protected Areas		1, 2, 3	Protection		EU Biodiversity Strategy	research
7	Commission guidance on defining, mapping and strictly protecting all primary and old-growth forests	ENV	Coherent Network of Protected Areas		1, 2, 3	Protection			regulators
8	Promote and support investments in green and blue infrastructure and cooperation among Member States to set up ecological corridors	ENV	Coherent Network of Protected Areas		1, 2, 3	Financing			regulators
9	Protect and restore ecosystems in the EU's Outermost Regions, and support biodiversity action in the Overseas Countries and Territories	ENV	Coherent Network of Protected Areas		1, 2, 3	Protection			regulators
10	Commission proposal for binding EU nature restoration targets	ENV	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Strengthening the EU legal framework for nature restoration	4	Restoration		Nature Restoration Law	industry
11	Commission guidance on the selection of species and habitats currently not in favorable conservation status for priority action	ENV	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Strengthening the EU legal framework for nature restoration	4	Protection			research

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Nr.	Title	Chef de File / DG	Area	Sub Area	GBF Target	Cluster	Driver	Linked Legislation	Affected group
12	Restore 30% of habitats and species currently not in favorable conservation status	ENV	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Strengthening the EU legal framework for nature restoration	4	Restoration			regulators
13	Commission guidance on an EU methodology to map, assess and achieve good condition of ecosystems so that they can deliver benefits	EEA, ENV, EUROSTAT, JRC	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Strengthening the EU legal framework for nature restoration	4	Support			research
14	Fully implement the EU Pollinators initiative	ENV	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Bringing nature back to agricultural land	5	Protection		EU Pollinators initiative	industry
16	Implement measures to reduce by 50% the overall use of - and risk from - chemical pesticides	SANTE	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Bringing nature back to agricultural land	6	Driver minimization	pollution	Sustainable Use of Pesticides Directive	industry
17	Commission proposal on revised Sustainable Use of Pesticides Directive	SANTE	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Bringing nature back to agricultural land	6	Driver minimization	pollution	Sustainable Use of Pesticides Directive	industry
18	Implement measures to ensure that at least 10% of agricultural area will be under high diversity landscape features by 2030	AGRI, ENV	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Bringing nature back to agricultural land	7	Driver minimization	pollution	CAP	industry
19	Constantly review progress on the target of 10% high-diversity landscape features and its possible impacts, and adjust if necessary	AGRI, ENV	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Bringing nature back to agricultural land	7	Driver minimization	land- and sea-use change		regulators
20	EU Action Plan on organic farming	AGRI	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Bringing nature back to agricultural land	8	Driver minimization	pollution	Action Plan on organic farming	industry
21	Take measures to ensure that Member States' CAP Strategic Plans set explicit national values for the relevant targets of the Biodiversity and Farm to Fork Strategies	AGRI	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Bringing nature back to agricultural land	8	Governance		CAP	regulators
22	Facilitate the registration of seed varieties for organic farming	SANTE	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Bringing nature back to agricultural land	8	Driver minimization	pollution		industry
23	Review marketing rules for traditional crop varieties in order to contribute to their conservation and sustainable use	SANTE	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Bringing nature back to agricultural land	8	Driver minimization	pollution		industry
24	Increase uptake of agroforestry support measures under rural development	AGRI, ENV	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Bringing nature back to agricultural land	8	Driver minimization	land- and sea-use change	CAP	industry

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Nr.	Title	Chef de File / DG	Area	Sub Area	GBF Target	Cluster	Driver	Linked Legislation	Affected group
25	EU Forest Strategy	AGRI, COM, ENV	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Forest quantity, health and resilience	8	Protection		EU Forest Strategy	industry
26	Further develop the Forest Information System for Europe (FISE)	ENV	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Forest quantity, health and resilience	8	Support		EU Forest Strategy	research
27	Work With Member States to ensure EU capacity to prevent and respond to major forest fires	AGRI, ECHO, ENV	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Forest quantity, health and resilience	8	Protection		CAP	regulators
28	Guidance on biodiversity-friendly afforestation and reforestation and closer-to-nature forestry	ENV	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Forest quantity, health and resilience	9	Protection			industry
29	Commission Roadmap for planting at least 3 billion additional trees in the EU by 2030 in full respect of ecological principles	ENV	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Forest quantity, health and resilience	9	Restoration		EU Forest Strategy	regulators
30	Encourage sustainable soil management practices, including as part of the CAP	AGRI, ENV	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Addressing land take and restoring soil ecosystems	10	Protection		EU Soil Strategy	industry
31	EU Soil Strategy	ENV	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Addressing land take and restoring soil ecosystems	10	Protection		EU Soil Strategy	industry
32	Identify contaminated soil sites, restore degraded soils, define the conditions for good ecological status and improve monitoring of soil quality	ENV	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Addressing land take and restoring soil ecosystems	10	Restoration		EU Biodiversity Strategy	regulators
33	EU Strategy for a Sustainable Built Environment	GROW	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Addressing land take and restoring soil ecosystems	10	Driver minimization	land- and sea-use change		industry
34	Support the development of solutions for restoring soil health and functions in the Horizon Europe Mission "Soil Deal for Europe"	ENV, RTD	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Addressing land take and restoring soil ecosystems	10	Protection			research
35	Minimize the use of whole trees and food and feed crops for energy production	ENER	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Win-win solutions for energy generation	10	Driver minimization	direct exploitation of organisms	RED II	industry

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Nr.	Title	Chef de File / DG	Area	Sub Area	GBF Target	Cluster	Driver	Linked Legislation	Affected group
36	Prioritize renewable energy solutions favorable to biodiversity	ENER	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Win-win solutions for energy generation	10	Driver minimization	climate change	RED II	industry
37	Regularly assess EU and global biomass supply and demand and related sustainability	JRC	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Win-win solutions for energy generation	10	Support			regulators
38	Review and revise the level of ambition of the Renewable Energy Directive (RED), the Emissions Trading Scheme (ETS), and Land Use, Land Use Change and Forestry (LULUCF)	COM, ENER	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Win-win solutions for energy generation	10	Governance		RED II, ETS, LULUCF	regulators
39	Publish a Study on the sustainability of the use of forest biomass for energy production	JRC, RTD	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Win-win solutions for energy generation	10	Support		RED II, ETS, LULUCF	research
40	Commission operational guidance on the new sustainability criteria on forest biomass for energy	ENER	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Win-win solutions for energy generation	10	Driver minimization	direct exploitation of organisms	RED II	industry
41	Review the data on biofuels with high indirect land-use change risk and set up a trajectory for their gradual phase out by 2030	ENER	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Win-win solutions for energy generation	10	Driver minimization	land- and sea-use change		research
42	Commission technical guidance and support to the Member States for the restoration of 25,000 km of free-flowing rivers	ENV	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Restoring freshwater ecosystems	11	Restoration		EU Biodiversity Strategy	regulators
43	Remove or adjust barriers and restore floodplains	ENV	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Restoring freshwater ecosystems	11	Restoration			industry
44	Provide technical support to Member States on their measures to review water abstraction and impoundment permits and to restore ecological flows	ENV	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Restoring freshwater ecosystems	11	Governance			regulators
45	Review water abstraction and impoundment permits to implement ecological flows and achieve good status or potential of all surface waters	ENV	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Restoring freshwater ecosystems	11	Restoration		WFD	regulators
46	Step up the implementation of the European Invasive Alien Species (IAS) Regulation	ENV	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Addressing invasive alien species	12	Driver minimization	invasive alien species	IAS Regulation	regulators
47	Take actions to reduce nutrient losses and pollution from nitrogen and phosphorus	ENV	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Reducing pollution	13	Driver minimization	pollution	Farm to Fork, Zero Pollution Action Plan	industry
48	Integrated Nutrient Management Action Plan	ENV	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Reducing pollution	13	Driver minimization	pollution	Farm to Fork, Zero Pollution Action Plan	industry

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Nr.	Title	Chef de File / DG	Area	Sub Area	GBF Target	Cluster	Driver	Linked Legislation	Affected group
49	Zero Pollution Action Plan for Air, Water and Soil	ENV	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Reducing pollution	13	Driver minimization	pollution	Zero Pollution Action Plan	industry
50	EU Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability	ENV	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Reducing pollution	13	Driver minimization	pollution		industry
51	Commission technical guidance on urban greening and assistance to mobilize funding and capacity building for the development and implementation of Urban Greening Plans	ENV	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Greening urban and peri-urban areas	14	Financing			regulators
52	EU Urban Greening Platform	ENV	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Greening urban and peri-urban areas	14	Support			regulators
53	Develop Urban Greening Plans	ENV	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Greening urban and peri-urban areas	14	Restoration			regulators
54	Implement measures to reduce and maintain fishing mortality at or under maximum sustainable yield	MARE	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Restoring marine ecosystems	15	Protection			industry
55	New Action Plan to conserve fisheries resources and protect marine ecosystems	ENV, MARE	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Restoring marine ecosystems	15	Protection		CFP, Natura 2000, MSFD	industry
56	Ensure consistency of national maritime spatial plans With the objectives of the EU Biodiversity Strategy	MARE	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Restoring marine ecosystems	15	Support			regulators
57	Establish fisheries management measures in marine protected areas	MARE	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Restoring marine ecosystems	s15	Protection		MSFD, CFP	industry
59	Ensure that Member States monitor by-catch, step up data collection and take measures to eliminate or, where not possible, to minimise by-catch	ENV, MARE	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Restoring marine ecosystems	16	Protection		MSFD	regulators
60	Put in Place an EU biodiversity governance framework	ENV	Enabling Transformative Change	A new governance framework		Governance		EU Biodiversity Strategy	regulators
61	Assess the effectiveness of the cooperation-based biodiversity governance framework, and the need for an enhanced approach to biodiversity governance	ENV	Enabling Transformative Change	A new governance framework		Governance			regulators

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Nr.	Title	Chef de File / DG	Area	Sub Area	GBF Target	Cluster	Driver	Linked Legislation	Affected group
62	Prioritize political support, financial and human resources to ensure full implementation and enforcement of environment-related legislation With impact on biodiversity	ENV	Enabling Transformative Change	Stepping up implementation and enforcement of EU environmental legislation		Governance			regulators
63	Improve environmental compliance assurance	ENV	Enabling Transformative Change	Stepping up implementation and enforcement of EU environmental legislation		Governance			regulators
64	Revise the Aarhus Regulation	ENV	Enabling Transformative Change	Stepping up implementation and enforcement of EU environmental legislation		Governance			regulators
65	Review and possibly revise the Environmental Crime Directive (ECD)	JUST	Enabling Transformative Change	Stepping up implementation and enforcement of EU environmental legislation		Governance			regulators
66	New sustainable corporate governance initiative addressing human rights, environmental duty of care and mandatory due diligence across value chains	JUST	Enabling Transformative Change	Business for biodiversity		Governance			industry
67	Continuously support the EU Business for Biodiversity movement	ENV	Enabling Transformative Change	Business for biodiversity		Support			industry
68	Review the reporting obligations of businesses under the Non-Financial Reporting Directive	FISMA	Enabling Transformative Change	Business for biodiversity		Financing		CSRD	industry

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Nr.	Title	Chef de File / DG	Area	Sub Area	GBF Target	Cluster	Driver	Linked Legislation	Affected group
69	Unlock at least 20 billion €/y for biodiversity and invest a significant proportion of the EU budget dedicated to climate action in biodiversity and nature-based solutions	BUDG	Enabling Transformative Change	Financing for biodiversity		Financing			regulators
70	Develop an EU-level Prioritized Action Framework	ENV	Enabling Transformative Change	Financing for biodiversity		Support		Habitats Directive	research
71	Develop a dedicated natural-capital and circular-economy initiative in the range of €10 billion over the next ten years	ECFIN, ENV	Enabling Transformative Change	Financing for biodiversity		Financing			research
72	Strengthen the biodiversity proofing framework to ensure that EU funding supports biodiversity-friendly investments	AGRI, BUDG, ECFIN, ENV, INTPA, MARE, REGIO	Enabling Transformative Change	Financing for biodiversity		Financing			research
73	Propose a Delegated Act under the Taxonomy Regulation With technical screening criteria fulfilling environmental objectives, including the protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems	FISMA	Enabling Transformative Change	Financing for biodiversity		Financing		Taxonomy Regulation	industry
74	Revise the Sustainable Finance Strategy	FISMA	Enabling Transformative Change	Financing for biodiversity		Financing			industry
75	Promote and encourage tax shifts to reflect environmental costs	ENV, FISMA	Enabling Transformative Change	Financing for biodiversity		Financing			regulators
76	Develop methods, criteria and standards to better integrate biodiversity considerations into public and business decision-making and to measure environmental footprint	ENV	Enabling Transformative Change	Measuring and integrating the value of nature (NCA)		Financing			industry
77	Promote an international natural capital accounting initiative	ENV	Enabling Transformative Change	Measuring and integrating the value of nature (NCA)		Financing			industry
78	Revise criteria and monitoring to encourage Nature Based Solutions for Green Public Procurement	ENV	Enabling Transformative Change	Measuring and integrating the value of nature (NCA)		Support		EU Sustainable Building	industry
79	Establish a Knowledge Centre for Biodiversity	ENV, JRC	Enabling Transformative Change	Knowledge		Support		EU Biodiversity Strategy	research

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Nr.	Title	Chef de File / DG	Area	Sub Area	GBF Target	Cluster	Driver	Linked Legislation	Affected group
80	Enable research, innovation and knowledge exchange between science, policy and society on biodiversity	ENV, MARE, RTD	Enabling Transformative Change	Knowledge		Support			research
81	Establish a Biodiversity Partnership under Horizon Europe	ENV, RTD	Enabling Transformative Change	Knowledge		Support			research
82	Propose a Council Recommendation on learning for environmental sustainability	EAC	Enabling Transformative Change	Education		Support			regulators
83	Broker an agreement for an ambitious post-2020 biodiversity framework at CBD COP15	ENV	EU External Action and an ambitious global biodiversity agenda	Raising the level of ambition and commitment worldwide		Governance			regulators
84	Launch or join High Ambition Coalitions	ENV	EU External Action and an ambitious global biodiversity agenda	Raising the level of ambition and commitment worldwide		Support			regulators
85	Broker an ambitious agreement on marine biological diversity of areas beyond national jurisdiction	MARE	EU External Action and an ambitious global biodiversity agenda	International Ocean Governance		Governance			regulators
86	Broker an agreement on three vast Marine Protected Areas in the Southern Ocean	MARE	EU External Action and an ambitious global biodiversity agenda	International Ocean Governance		Governance			regulators
87	Advocate that marine minerals in the international seabed area cannot be exploited before the effects of deep-sea mining on the marine environment have been sufficiently researched, and advocate for increased transparency in the International Seabed Authority	MARE	EU External Action and an ambitious global biodiversity agenda	International Ocean Governance		Governance			research
88	Engage in WTO negotiations towards a global agreement to ban harmful fisheries subsidies	TRADE	EU External Action and an ambitious global biodiversity agenda	Trade policy		Driver minimization	land- and sea-use change		regulators
89	Ensure full implementation and enforcement of biodiversity provisions in all trade agreements	TRADE	EU External Action and an ambitious global biodiversity agenda	Trade policy		Governance			industry
90	Improve the assessment of the impact of trade agreements on biodiversity and strengthen biodiversity provisions of existing and new agreements if relevant	TRADE	EU External Action and an ambitious global biodiversity agenda	Trade policy		Governance			industry

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Nr.	Title	Chef de File / DG	Area	Sub Area	GBF Target	Cluster	Driver	Linked Legislation	Affected group
91	Legislative proposal and measures to avoid or minimize the placing of products associated with deforestation or forest degradation on the EU market	ENV	EU External Action and an ambitious global biodiversity agenda	Deforestation, wildlife trafficking, illicit trade		Driver minimization	direct exploitation of organisms	Timber Regulation	industry
92	Revise the Action plan against Wildlife Trafficking	ENV	EU External Action and an ambitious global biodiversity agenda	Deforestation, wildlife trafficking, illicit trade		Driver minimization	direct exploitation of organisms	Action Plan on wildlife trafficking	regulators
93	Propose a further tightening of the EU rules on ivory trade	ENV	EU External Action and an ambitious global biodiversity agenda	Deforestation, wildlife trafficking, illicit trade		Driver minimization	direct exploitation of organisms	Environmental Crime Directive	regulators
94	Consider strengthening the coordinating and investigative capacities for biodiversity of the European Anti-Fraud Office	OLAF	EU External Action and an ambitious global biodiversity agenda	Deforestation, wildlife trafficking, illicit trade		Governance			regulators
95	Mobilize Aid for Trade to ensure that EU partner countries reap the benefits of biodiversity-friendly trade	INTPA, TRADE	EU External Action and an ambitious global biodiversity agenda	Deforestation, wildlife trafficking, illicit trade		Support			regulators
96	Increase support to partner countries for protection, ecosystem restoration and the sustainable management of natural resources	INTPA, NEAR	EU External Action and an ambitious global biodiversity agenda	International cooperation, neighborhood policy and resource mobilization		Financing			regulators
97	Support the Western Balkans and EU Neighborhood countries in their efforts to protect, sustainably use, restore and mainstream biodiversity	NEAR	EU External Action and an ambitious global biodiversity agenda	International cooperation, neighborhood policy and resource mobilization		Financing			regulators
98	Implement NaturAfrica and other integrated regional and multi-country initiative	INTPA	EU External Action and an ambitious global biodiversity agenda	International cooperation, neighborhood policy and resource mobilization		Support			regulators

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Nr.	Title	Chef de File / DG	Area	Sub Area	GBF Target	Cluster	Driver	Linked Legislation	Affected group
99	Systematically strengthen links between biodiversity protection and sustainable socio-economic development in partner countries	INTPA	EU External Action and an ambitious global biodiversity agenda	International cooperation, neighborhood policy and resource mobilization		Governance			regulators
100	Support global efforts to apply the One Health approach	SANTE	EU External Action and an ambitious global biodiversity agenda	International cooperation, neighborhood policy and resource mobilization		Governance			regulators
101	Mainstream Biodiversity throughout bilateral and multilateral engagements	EEAS, FPI, INTPA, NEAR	EU External Action and an ambitious global biodiversity agenda	International cooperation, neighborhood policy and resource mobilization		Governance			regulators
102	Mid-term review of the Biodiversity Strategy	ENV	EU External Action and an ambitious global biodiversity agenda	Review of progress		Governance			regulators
15a	Commission report on the review of progress in the implementation of the EU Pollinators initiative	ENV	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Bringing nature back to agricultural land	5	Governance		EU Pollinators initiative	regulators
15b	Revise the EU Pollinators Initiative	AGRI, ENV, SANTE	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Bringing nature back to agricultural land	5	Protection		EU Pollinators initiative	regulators
58a	Establish seabed integrity threshold values	ENV	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Restoring marine ecosystems	15	Protection		MSFD	regulators
58b	Support the transition to more selective and less damaging fishing techniques through the European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund	MARE	EU Nature Restoration Plan	Restoring marine ecosystems	15	Financing			industry

Table 17: Appendix 2c: EU Strategic actions

Appendix 3: Biodiversity Finance Landscape

Appendix 3a: Issued and outstanding green bonds per credit rating category (Bloomberg)

Row Labels	Sum of Par Amt USD	Sum of Amt Issued USD	Sum of Amt Out USD
A	\$ 5,070,941.23	\$ 99,670,498,305.65	\$ 99,670,498,305.65
A-	\$ 6,800,597.41	\$ 129,795,184,025.04	\$ 129,732,389,657.04
A*-	\$ 12,358.18	\$ 839,115,780.00	\$ 839,115,780.00
A+	\$ 3,537,894.57	\$ 27,576,090,809.10	\$ 26,820,232,422.60
A-1+	\$ 15,219.49	\$ 4,565,847.00	\$ 4,565,847.00
A-2	\$ 923.74	\$ 83,136,240.00	\$ 83,136,240.00
AA	\$ 1,347,435.15	\$ 23,391,373,510.54	\$ 23,391,373,510.54
AA-	\$ 488,072.52	\$ 18,238,983,851.97	\$ 17,937,351,818.41
AA+	\$ 913,913.55	\$ 73,951,612,175.96	\$ 73,951,612,175.96
AAA	\$ 5,961,579.72	\$ 180,243,918,902.50	\$ 181,754,098,738.41
B	\$ 11,880.38	\$ 7,404,384,925.00	\$ 7,276,506,586.07
B-	\$ 4,440.00	\$ 2,153,400,000.00	\$ 2,147,850,000.00
B+	\$ 19,033.26	\$ 11,110,811,260.00	\$ 11,034,298,960.00
BB	\$ 591,351.63	\$ 25,232,286,114.19	\$ 23,872,985,661.80
BB-	\$ 18,354.73	\$ 9,263,018,386.00	\$ 8,238,674,866.00
BB- *+	\$ 1,685.54	\$ 1,516,984,200.00	\$ 1,213,587,360.00
BB+	\$ 1,965,646.46	\$ 46,281,461,607.30	\$ 45,391,313,335.54
BB+ *-	\$ 1,637.10	\$ 654,838,400.00	\$ 654,838,400.00
BBB	\$ 5,441,970.11	\$ 156,236,486,997.94	\$ 154,826,326,345.10
BBB-	\$ 4,858,681.20	\$ 81,120,087,471.60	\$ 74,592,937,103.39
BBB *	\$ 984.10	\$ 344,841,924.00	\$ 344,841,924.00
BBB *-	\$ 2,644.22	\$ 1,057,688,400.00	\$ 1,057,688,400.00
BBB- *-	\$ 169,398.85	\$ 3,189,126,930.00	\$ 3,189,126,930.00
BBB- *+	\$ 2,220.00	\$ 1,665,000,000.00	\$ 1,665,000,000.00
BBB+	\$ 11,978,150.68	\$ 193,027,809,971.55	\$ 191,438,133,121.55
NR	\$ 476,160.29	\$ 12,904,509,533.16	\$ 11,230,937,169.47

Table 18: Appendix 3a: Green bonds par amounts, issuance, and outstandings per credit rating

Appendix 3a: Issued and outstanding sustainability-linked bonds per credit rating category (Bloomberg)

	Sum of Par Amt USD	Sum of Amt Issued USD	Sum of Amt Out USD
A	\$ 3,508,470.22	\$ 34,624,283,748.00	\$ 34,624,283,748.00
A-	\$ 273,489.56	\$ 34,257,479,600.00	\$ 34,257,479,600.00
A+	\$ 8,127,271.27	\$ 26,199,233,820.00	\$ 25,750,233,820.00
AA	\$ 2,280,748.30	\$ 53,301,714,273.60	\$ 52,737,900,379.60
AA-	\$ 662,378.86	\$ 7,552,539,213.78	\$ 7,552,539,213.78
AA+	\$ 300,991.59	\$ 35,429,847,822.00	\$ 35,429,847,822.00
AAA	\$ 28,674,610.16	\$ 311,343,796,017.75	\$ 311,015,179,254.90
AAAp	\$ 7,487,331.79	\$ 924,280,204.93	\$ 924,280,204.93
B+ **	\$ 1,207.48	\$ 1,207,480,000.00	\$ 602,749,866.40
BB	\$ 234,191.00	\$ 4,052,017,500.00	\$ 4,052,017,500.00
BB-	\$ 10,390.14	\$ 5,286,008,250.00	\$ 5,158,701,250.00
BB+	\$ 3,000.00	\$ 1,050,000,000.00	\$ 1,024,459,000.00
BBB	\$ 582,492.93	\$ 28,089,125,922.96	\$ 27,092,132,922.96
BBB-	\$ 343,626.13	\$ 11,965,181,000.00	\$ 11,965,181,000.00
BBB+	\$ 3,487,510.33	\$ 22,902,626,127.00	\$ 22,819,523,822.06
NR	\$ 329,800.84	\$ 2,967,639,000.00	\$ 2,967,639,000.00

Table 19: Appendix 3a: Sustainability-Linked bond par amounts, issuance, and outstandings per credit rating

Appendix 3b: Biodiversity Investors (PRI)

Year	Total Signatories	BD Signatories	BD-IM	BD-AO	STR BD	BD Standard	BD community	LE BD	FI BD	PE BD	RE BD	INF BD	HF BD	BD incl UK	Bur	BD Asia	BD Americas	BD Oceania	BD Africa	BD Cayman & Bermuda
2016	1030	31	15	16	6	4	4	15	11	12	11	9	0	71 %		3 %	3 %	16 %	6 %	3 %
2017	1187	86	63	23	34	8	7	19	16	7	14	16	0	67 %		5 %	10 %	12 %	3 %	2 %
2018	1365	118	90	28	55	6	6	19	19	8	16	21	0	66 %		3 %	17 %	9 %	3 %	2 %
2019	1704	207	171	36	111	15	12	21	35	25	24	34	1	65 %		4 %	16 %	10 %	3 %	1 %
2020	2099	238	196	42	121	21	14	30	39	13	32	50	3	67 %		5 %	18 %	10 %	1 %	0 %

Table 20: Appendix 3b: Biodiversity foci of PRI signatories

IM = Investment Manager, AO = Asset Owner, LE = Listed Equity, FI = Fixed Income, PE = Private Equity, RE = Real Estate, INF = Infrastructure, HF = Hedge Funds

Year	Mentioned Standards/guidelines/recommendations
2016	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IFC Performance Standards on Social and Environmental Sustainability World Bank Environmental, Health and Safety Guidelines International Union for Conservation of Nature (Biodiversity) Nagoya Biodiversity Summit Natural Capital Declaration Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative Earth Charter and Rio Conventions on Biodiversity
2017	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Convention on Biological Diversity 1992 Millenium Ecosystem Assessment 2001 International Union for Conservation of Nature (Biodiversity) IFC Performance Standards on Social and Environmental Sustainability Earth Charter Nagoya Biodiversity Summit
2018	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Convention on Biodiversity and Protocol on Biosecurity ISO 9001 Pan European Forest Council (PEFC) Farmland principles Nagoya Biodiversity Summit
2019	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IFC Performance Standards on Social and Environmental Sustainability Science based Targets

Year	Mentioned Standards/guidelines/recommendations
	Forest certifications (FSC, SFI, PEFC) GRI Green Bonds Principles Carbon Disclosure Project ISO9001 Climate Community and Biodiversity Standard (CCBS)
2020	Rio Declaration on Environment and Development, IFC Performance Standards on Social and Environmental Sustainability ISO 9001 TCFD Carbon Disclosure Project FAIRR initiative 2 degrees investing Community & Biodiversity Standards (carbon credits) Science based Targets Transition Pathway Initiative (TPI) Paris Agreement Capital Transition Assessment (PACTA) (then still anticipated) EU Sustainable Finance Taxonomy US Carbon Forestry strategy Forest Stewardship Council (FSC) Standards Nagoya Biodiversity Summit

Table 21: Appendix 3b: PRI signatories' biodiversity community engagement

This project is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 101082057.